

**A MENTORING PROGRAM FOR ENHANCING ENGAGEMENT AND
PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT: AN APPLIED IMPROVEMENT PROJECT**

by

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Abstract

The Applied Improvement Project (AIP) is a comprehensive initiative to enhance part-time faculty members' participation and professional development in meetings and training. The Problem of Practice is that part-time faculty are not actively participating in quarterly faculty meetings. The primary objective of the AIP is to address the challenges part-time faculty members face in accessing and benefiting from the meeting opportunities. Recognizing the valuable contributions of these faculty members to the academic community, the AIP is designed to foster an environment that encourages their development and active participation, ensuring inclusivity and support. The AIP consists of several critical components designed to achieve its objectives. These include developing and implementing a mentoring program, providing resources, and training opportunities, and establishing a feedback mechanism for continuous improvement. The mentoring program pairs part-time faculty members with experienced mentors who provide guidance, support, and career advice. This program enhances part-time faculty members' professional development and overall job satisfaction. Various measures have been taken to ensure the effectiveness, credibility, and validity of the AIP. These measures include providing data collection and analysis confidentiality, using reliable measurement tools, and addressing potential biases in implementing the mentoring program. The expected outcomes of the AIP include increased participation of part-time faculty members in meetings and training, improved job satisfaction and motivation, enhanced professional growth, and improved academic outcomes. By empowering part-time faculty members and providing them with the necessary support and resources, the AIP established a collaborative and inclusive educational environment.

Dedication

To God Almighty, whose grace and guidance have illuminated my path at every step. To my beloved mother, whose wisdom and encouragement guided me towards the path of education, her influence has been my compass. To my dear wife and children, the backbone of my doctoral journey. This achievement is not just mine, but a testament to the strength and inspiration they have all provided me.

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INTRODUCTION

Southeastern Community College (SCC), a pseudonym used for anonymity, encompasses an educational network with seven campus locations and an extensive array of degree and certificate programs. It serves the academic needs of nearly 21,000 students and boasts a faculty and staff of approximately 3,000 members. It is a thriving educational community with a mission to transform lives and inspire students to excellence. However, the Problem of Practice is that few part-time faculty members participate in quarterly faculty meetings and professional development opportunities. This lack of collaboration and team effort can result in workplace failures, including a lack of curriculum advancements, limited participation in professional development, a lack of institutional knowledge, and overworking of committed faculty. To address this Problem of Practice, an Applied Improvement Project was developed using the AIP model, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Applied Improvement Project Model

Note. From *Applied Improvement Project Model*, by the University, 2024. CC BY-NC. Reprinted with permission.

The target audience for this project is the part-time faculty members of one of the departments in SCC called the Division. The Division faculty comprises 28 full-time and 77 part-time faculty members. The AIP focused to strengthen the Division through collaboration, encouraging part-time faculty members to become vested in the organization and contribute to improving the educational system. Since 73% of the teaching faculty comprises part-time faculty, solving this problem will significantly impact the students. Part-time faculty members are often the primary point of contact for students representing the institution. By actively participating in quarterly faculty meetings and professional development opportunities, they will gain valuable information about the institution, which they can then share with students. This support will help students stay motivated and maintain a sense of commitment to their learning process, as they will receive accurate information about facilities and college activities from these faculty members. Moreover, the students will benefit from enhanced teaching quality as both part-time and full-time faculty work collaboratively to make improvements in their disciplines. By fostering collaboration and teamwork, the AIP will ensure that curriculum advancements and institutional knowledge are shared among faculty members, resulting in a more cohesive and effective educational experience for the students.

The key stakeholders in this matter are the Dean of the Division and his Department Chairs, whose primary interest lies in achieving academic excellence within the institution. Addressing the issue and implementing necessary improvements is essential to achieve this goal. The researcher involved in this project is a full-time faculty member with firsthand experience with the challenges part-time faculty face. Having started as a part-time faculty member, the researcher understands the lack of belongingness and the resulting disengagement from faculty meetings and professional development opportunities. During their time as a part-time faculty

member, the researcher faced limited support and guidance from other faculty members. Now, as a full-time faculty member, the researcher is actively involved in informal mentoring with new faculty members. Drawing from their experiences as a new faculty member, the researcher helps others understand their tasks and navigate the challenges they may encounter. However, it is essential to note that this mentoring model did not follow a structured approach for success. Through this Action Plan, the researcher has developed a model incorporating the three phases of an Applied Improvement Project (AIP). The model addresses part-time faculty members' issues and fosters a sense of belongingness and engagement within the institution.

This monograph is a comprehensive overview of each section, from the evaluation to the implementation phase, outlining the steps and strategies required for the program's success. The Applied Improvement Project (AIP) model, depicted in Figure 1, is a structured problem-solving approach encompassing various phases, including planning, implementation, and evaluation. During the planning phase, the project engaged in stage 1 of the model, which involved diagnosing the problem. The researcher conducted a needs assessment to identify the problem of practice and determine potential root causes. The literature review was a comprehensive analysis of the factors contributing to the performance gap among part-time faculty. Based on the findings from the literature review, strategies were developed to address the identified issues and enhance outcomes for part-time faculty. Alternatives were generated, and an action plan was meticulously designed.

The AIP Action Plan is a detailed plan to address the identified Problem of Practice. This plan encompassed several vital steps, including identifying potential solutions, selecting the most suitable approach, and formulating an implementation plan. Various possible solutions were considered, such as implementing a mentoring model, fostering support from full-time faculty

towards part-time faculty, establishing an online resource center, and promoting collaborative work. Each potential solution was thoroughly evaluated, considering stakeholder input and the institution's mission and goals. The best approach was selected, and a detailed action plan was created, outlining the necessary steps and strategies for successful implementation. This action plan included a timeline for implementation, a budget section delineating the required resources, and a data collection plan to evaluate the program's effectiveness.

The implementation phase encompassed two sections: mentor training and the actual mentoring process involving two mentee participants. In this study, the researcher actively engaged in mentor training and assumed the role of a mentor. An AIP implementation journal was employed to monitor and document the process. Following the mentor training, mentor participants completed a training survey to gather their valuable insights and ideas on effectively guiding a mentoring relationship. This feedback was crucial in refining the mentor training program for future iterations, ensuring continuous improvement. Before commencing the mentoring interventions, in-depth interviews were conducted with the two mentee participants to understand their perspectives on mentoring and expectations. These interviews provided valuable insights into the mentees' specific needs and goals, enabling the mentoring approach to be tailored accordingly.

Upon the completion of the implementation phase, the mentees participated in mentor evaluation forms to assess the impact of the mentoring program on their professional journeys and determine if it effectively addressed the problem of practice. This evaluation process allowed for a thorough examination of the program's outcomes. The mentoring interventions were scheduled for five weeks, with each mentee participant engaging in weekly meetings with their mentor to discuss specific topics. These topics were identified in the initial meeting following the

interviews, ensuring the mentoring sessions were customized to cater to the mentees' interests and needs. The participants had access to a mentoring Canvas course, which provided them with supplementary materials and surveys related to mentoring to enhance the mentoring experience.

Additionally, the mentor created a Microsoft Teams notebook for each participant, facilitating communication and establishing contact through the Teams chat platform. These Microsoft Teams notebooks included action plans incorporating specific interventions and topics for the five weeks. After week 5, the mentee participants completed mentoring evaluation forms, while the mentor submitted an end-of-mentoring survey. This comprehensive evaluation allowed for a holistic assessment of the effectiveness of the mentoring program.

SECTION 1. PLANNING

The planning section of the mentoring program is organized, encompassing several crucial elements. It commences with a clear statement of the problem of practice, identifying the issue of lack of part-time faculty participation in quarterly meetings. The community and organizational context are then explored, providing valuable insights into the environment where the mentoring intervention will occur. The intervention and solution are discussed, and the proposed strategies and approaches to address the identified problem are outlined. A purpose statement articulates the objectives and goals of the program. A review of relevant literature is conducted to establish a theoretical foundation and support for the mentoring intervention. Additionally, the planning section explains the applied improvement project methods, outlining the specific steps and methodologies employed. Limitations are acknowledged to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the project's scope and potential constraints. Credibility is maintained using reliable sources and robust research methodologies. Ethical and regulatory considerations are also addressed to ensure compliance with ethical guidelines and regulatory requirements. This organized planning section establishes a solid foundation for the mentoring program, setting the stage for its effective implementation and evaluation.

Statement of the Problem

The Problem of Practice is that part-time faculty are not actively participating in quarterly faculty meetings. These meetings occur at various levels within the department, division, and college, offering valuable opportunities for professional development, discussion of new trends, student resources, and collaborative activities. The Dean's data reveals that an average of 86% of part-time faculty do not attend these crucial meetings. (The Dean of the Division, personal communication, January 18, 2023)

Considering that part-time faculty constitute a significant portion of the teaching community, their lack of involvement in collaboration and team efforts can lead to various workplace challenges. These challenges include stagnation in curriculum advancements, limited participation in professional development, a lack of institutional knowledge, and an increased burden on committed faculty members. As Danaei (2019) highlighted, adjuncts often find themselves excluded from institutional discussions concerning learning objectives, course assignments, textbook selections, professional development opportunities, evaluation processes, and feedback mechanisms. Consequently, the non-participation of part-time faculty in quarterly faculty meetings deprives them of valuable opportunities to learn and contribute to new trends, student resources, and activities.

Community/Organizational Context

SCC faces the critical challenge of effectively engaging part-time faculty in essential activities, such as quarterly faculty meetings, amidst their other commitments. Despite the part-time handbook's clear mandates, a significant number of faculty members cite external obligations as barriers to participation. This issue not only impacts the operational dynamics of the college but also contradicts the administration's assumption that part-time faculty will seamlessly integrate into our collaborative, learning-centered culture. Under the new President's direction, the shift to online learning platforms and the strategic increase in part-time instructors aim to address growing student enrollment in a cost-effective manner. However, the persistent gap in meeting participation highlights a disconnect between administrative expectations and the realities faced by part-time faculty. The advanced improvement project, involving key stakeholders, seeks to reconcile these differences and enhance community engagement within the academic environment.

The Problem and Its History

There has been a noticeable lack of participation in quarterly faculty meetings, which has raised concerns. The Dean recognizes the need to motivate and engage part-time faculty members, fostering a more substantial commitment to the college. Gappa and Leslie (1993) assert that motivational factors such as personal and professional growth, status, and the potential for a full-time academic position can drive part-time faculty participation. However, it is discouraging to note that 86% of part-time faculty members cannot participate due to other commitments and full-time employment elsewhere. This issue has far-reaching implications for the college community, as part-time faculty members constitute a significant percentage of the teaching population. According to the Dean of the Division, part-time faculty account for 73% of the teaching faculty within the institution. (The Dean of the Division, personal communication, January 18, 2023)

To qualify as part-time faculty at SCC, candidates undergo a pre-employment screening for each job classification. Once they are considered, a background check determines the final employment decision. Part-time faculty are limited to three classes per semester, and they cannot expect future employment since their contract does not include an award of a continuing contract. According to the part-time handbook, the average part-time faculty makes approximately \$40,000 annually. Their responsibilities include creating and providing their dean with a syllabus, maintaining accurate course and grade records, and completing the required student reporting. The part-time handbook mentions that faculty must participate in the new-hire training sessions and college-wide required training and attend mandatory college, department, division, and discipline meetings. If the necessary services are not completed, the institution may withhold the final pay installment until duties have been completed. Despite the requirements,

according to the Dean's attendance records, most adjunct faculty do not participate in mandatory faculty meetings. There is no data to confirm why this duty has not been enforced. Still, there are several actions the institution adopted to mitigate the issue. They provide free-of-cost faculty development to encourage educational advancements. They offer appealing courses such as active learning, online teaching, and collaborative strategies. The faculty development department also provides an incentive plan that translates into hourly raises for part-timers who participate in specific training opportunities the institution offers. Part-time faculty can enroll for free in courses offered at any campus location. While these benefits appeal to some faculty members, there has not been a significant change in the number of part-time faculty members participating in these activities. In conversations with part-time faculty stakeholders and non-stakeholders, the reasons for not participating are low pay, lack of time and knowledge of college offerings, and motivation to participate.

The Organization's Mission and Values

In 1995, the board of trustees officially endorsed the organization's mission. This endorsement was a move to embrace a philosophy centered around learning. The organization committed itself to fostering an environment where education, growth, and development are paramount by adopting a learning-centered approach. This commitment is articulated through the organization's mission, vision, and values, which collectively guide its strategic direction and daily operations.

The Mission

SCC's mission is "to provide academic, technical, and life-long learning opportunities in a collaborative culture dedicated to inquiry, results, and excellence." (institution website data).

The Vision

SCC is a premier learning institution that “strives to transform lives, strengthen the community, and inspire individuals to excellence.” (institution website data).

The Values

SCC is committed to learning and caring for the people they serve by “supporting an inclusive environment, fostering diversity, reaching out to communities, and respecting the integrity of everyone.” (institution website data). The institution is vested in an educational community with a strong collaborative culture that supports professional development, career growth, and the healthy lives of the employees.

The Organization's Political, Social and Economic Culture

SCC is politically a state organization under the local control of a Board of Trustees appointed by the governor. They have the legal decision-making power in college policy, programs, building, budget, and personnel. In 2022, a significant change in the political culture of the institution occurred, with the board appointing a new President. The new President of the college has brought about more substantial change in the political culture of the institution by implementing a few initiatives. One of the most notable changes has been the increase in student enrollment. The COVID-19 pandemic impacted the learning community and resulted in a decrease in enrollment. However, the new President successfully transitioned most of the institution's face-to-face platform to online learning, which attracted a larger pool of learners. In addition, the President has also tried to hire more part-time instructors. By hiring more part-time instructors, the President can cost-effectively cover the increase in student enrollment since part-time instructors are typically hired on a contractual basis and are paid for the number of hours they work.

SCC's social culture is to provide quality education at an affordable cost, offering the same education as a state university, with smaller campuses and classes, only about half the price to serve the southeastern population. The institution believes low-cost education impacts student success. Affordability also welcomes diversity. Currently, there are nearly 100 countries represented on campus, but the most significant population is Hispanic. This population is also due to SCC having five campuses in two counties with a large Hispanic population. The institution values cultural differences and encourages students to learn about and accept people from diverse ethnic and cultural backgrounds.

Considering the economical culture, the college's financial stability largely depends on various sources such as tuition fees, grants and contracts from the state and counties, state college funds, lottery funds, gifts, and college facility usage services. However, budget constraints may present an economic barrier. The stakeholders have expressed concerns that the budget is limited. The division, the largest division of the SCC, has already reached its capacity for hiring or making budget adjustments. If necessary, the stakeholders must meet with their budget managers to explore the possibility of adjusting the budget.

Mental Models and Assumptions of the Problem by Administrators and Stakeholders

Part-time faculty will become self-reliant and flexible in Senior Leaderships' mental models. They assume the part-time faculty will embrace a collaborative culture, attend professional development training, and participate in quarterly faculty meetings. Despite the mental models, only 14% of adjunct instructors participate in department, division, and college-wide forums such as quarterly faculty meetings.

The Dean's mental model is that part-time faculty are not vested, and the institution needs to figure out how to solve this problem. The root of the problem is directed toward

teamwork. He assumes that the institution needs to focus on finding ways to encourage cooperation and collaboration. He also believes he can do little at the division level if collaboration efforts do not occur spontaneously. The data shows that full-time faculty are more involved in collaborating efforts than part-time faculty. Despite his assumptions, he is willing to support a possible solution at the division level. (Dean of Division, personal communication, January 18, 2023)

The Department Chair has a different mental model. In her mental model, the Division leaders do not communicate effectively with the part-time faculty. She mentioned that the institution needs to adopt suitable communication strategies through technology. She assumes that information can be streamlined through a part-time faculty online center where they can get all necessary information related to the department, division, and college activities. She also believes that the departments should encourage group messaging to discuss matters in which everyone's opinions are necessary. (Department Chair, stakeholder meeting, February 3, 2023)

Organizational Factors in Support of Improvement Project

Despite the leadership's commitment and understanding of the need for intervention, previous attempts have not been successful. The program faces challenges such as a lack of faculty commitment, participation resistance, and budget constraints. These obstacles highlight the importance of finding effective solutions to ensure AIP's success in fostering a more inclusive and participatory environment. To address these issues, leaders have explored innovative strategies to bypass budget limitations and enhance faculty engagement. Additionally, fostering a culture that values collaboration and community participation is vital in overcoming resistance and building a stronger sense of belonging among part-time faculty.

Organizational Support

The leader of the division is the Dean, who oversees six departments. Each department has been affected by the issue. They have attempted interaction solutions that have failed. The leadership team understands that there needs to be an intervention where the part-time faculty will develop a sense of belonging and participate in quarterly faculty meetings. Their support structure will allow access to data related to the problem. Since they are vested in finding a successful solution, they will act as critical stakeholders to help reduce and uncover issues, constraints, and risks. Having their support will result in success for the AIP's success.

Organizational Barriers

Several organizational factors could hinder the improvement of the project process. First, there is a lack of understanding of the importance of belonging to a collaborative community. Many part-time faculty do not see a priority in participating in quarterly faculty meetings. The only commitment they have is within their classroom hours. These faculty might not cooperate with the improvement project. Second, there could be resistance to collaborating with the improvement project due to lack of time, conflict of interest, or conflictive ideas. The economic factor that might also present a barrier to the advanced improvement project is budget limits. A solution might require resources such as hiring new personnel or purchasing materials, equipment, and services. The leadership team has expressed that the budget is constrained because the division, the largest division of SCC, has reached its budget capacity for hiring or making any budget adjustments. If necessary, the stakeholders must figure out how to address this. The leaders must meet with their budget managers to determine if they can adjust it.

Collaboration with Site Members

Four site members are collaborating with this advanced improvement project: the Dean of

the Division, the Department Chair, the head of the faculty development department, and one part-time faculty. These four individuals are vested in this Advanced Improvement Project and agree that the problem of practice is an issue worth finding a solution to. There have been several communication efforts to address the problem of practice and explore potential interventions.

The Dean

The Dean of the Division is the main stakeholder. He oversees the largest division of the institution, composed of five disciplines and seven departments. Since he is the top decision-maker, communication and collaboration are vital. There have been several one-on-one conversations regarding the problem of practice. He has demonstrated his support by providing essential data, participating in the first stakeholder meeting, and lending literature resources that will help support a successful implementation.

The Department Chair

The Department Chair is also a primary stakeholder. She coordinates and supervises the faculty. She is primarily interested in this AIP; therefore, there has been constant communication. Her ideas and recommendations have been discussed in the stakeholders' meeting, making them part of the potential interventions.

The Mentoring Committee

The Mentoring Committee is an essential organization established by the Dean to provide robust support for the mentoring project. Composed of dedicated full-time and adjunct faculty members who have demonstrated a genuine interest in mentoring, their stakeholder roles encompass many responsibilities. These include actively supporting the development of a comprehensive mentoring program, assisting in the recruitment of both mentors and mentees, offering valuable insights and recommendations for pairing suitable mentor-mentee

relationships, providing unwavering support during training and orientation sessions, and actively participating in the evaluation process to ensure the program's effectiveness and success.

Intervention/Solution

The initial step in the Applied Improvement Project (AIP) was to identify the Problem of Practice, which encompassed the low levels of participation and engagement from part-time faculty members in quarterly faculty meetings at Southeastern Community College. Following a comprehensive needs assessment, the intervention strategy involved the development of a mentoring program specifically tailored for part-time faculty members. This program aimed to enhance part-time faculty's understanding of institutional processes and foster a sense of belonging, ultimately motivating them to engage more actively in quarterly faculty meetings. The program's design included the involvement of full-time faculty members serving as mentors to their part-time counterparts, providing them with assistance and guidance to help them succeed in their roles. Stakeholders were dedicated to promoting collaborative work, implementing effective mentoring models, identifying full-time staff to serve as mentors, and establishing an online center for part-time faculty. The subsequent section outlines the proposed solutions or interventions to address the Problem of Practice in collaboration with stakeholders. These solutions or interventions are designed to support and encourage part-time faculty to invest time beyond teaching and become active members of their department, division, and the college community.

Development of Proposed Actions and Collaboration with Stakeholders

During the first week of the proposal development, discussions were held with stakeholders to deliberate on the problem of practice and the proposed actions. By the third week, all stakeholders were brought together in a meeting to finalize the adjustments to the

proposal. Initially, the problem of practice in the AIP centered on strategies to encourage part-time faculty participation in college activities. However, it was collectively decided that a more effective approach would be to explore ways part-time faculty could become more deeply invested in collaborative efforts through active participation in faculty team meetings (Stakeholder Meeting, 2023). The strategies and actions were developed after identifying four primary root causes, as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1

Proposed Interventions

Potential Solution/Intervention	Cause Solution/Intervention Addresses
1. Implement a mentoring model	The lack of mentoring leads part-time faculty members to not understand their roles and not be motivated to attend faculty team meetings. A mentoring program that pairs them with experienced colleagues will ensure lack of guidance is no longer an issue for part-time faculty.
2. Encourage full-time faculty to support part-time faculty.	The lack of support from full-time faculty may lead to a poor collaborative environment. Promoting a collaborative culture will ensure that part-time faculty feel valued and motivated to participate in team meetings.
3. Create a database or online center focused on part-time faculty.	Limited access to institutional resources can lead to feelings of isolation and lack of engagement with the institution. An online center will meet the specific needs of part-time faculty, allowing them to become more connected with the institution. This will increase their engagement and participation in faculty team meetings.
4. Encourage continued collaborative work	The lack of teamwork leads to a poor collaborative environment. By encouraging teamwork opportunities, the part-time faculty will foster a sense of community and increase participation in team meetings.

The stakeholders agreed that establishing mentoring models to support part-time faculty would be an effective intervention. They understood that a mentoring program would offer part-time faculty opportunities to learn from experienced colleagues, develop new skills, and advance their careers. The first step will involve defining the objectives of the mentoring program, which

will be crucial in shaping the desired outcomes. The next step will be to identify suitable mentors and mentees. Mentees will be paired with full-time faculty with greater experience, skills, and compatible personalities. This careful matching will ensure a productive and mutually beneficial relationship. Furthermore, mentors and mentees will undergo training to familiarize themselves with their new roles and responsibilities. Once they have a clear understanding of their roles, they can start their mentoring sessions. Eventually, both parties must evaluate the mentoring intervention to assess its effectiveness and offer insights for future mentoring relationships.

The second intervention, detailed in Table 1, focuses on the leadership team's efforts to promote a culture of inclusivity and support within the department, particularly encouraging full-time faculty members to support their part-time colleagues. This initiative aims to bridge the gap between full-time and part-time faculty through enhanced communication and collaboration. Regular meetings, collaborative projects, and shared departmental goals are strategies that will be employed to foster this sense of community and teamwork. Additionally, the intervention includes plans for recognizing and appreciating the contributions of all faculty members, regardless of their employment status. This recognition will boost morale and emphasize the value of each individual's work towards the department's success.

Establishing a database or online center designed to cater to the unique needs of part-time faculty members represents a significant step toward supporting their professional and personal growth. This centralized hub will offer easy access to a wealth of information, including essential teaching resources, opportunities for professional development, and comprehensive details on benefits and compensation. Furthermore, including a dedicated forum and communication system will facilitate a vibrant community where part-time faculty can engage with one another. Within this community, they can share experiences, offer advice, and exchange best practices,

fostering a sense of belonging and collaboration. By providing these resources and a platform for connection, the database or online center aims to enhance the overall experience and effectiveness of part-time faculty within the academic institution.

The leadership team, including the Dean and Department Chairs, will commit to facilitating collaboration between part-time and full-time faculty members by creating opportunities for joint projects. This approach will help faculty members work together, learning from each other's strengths and weaknesses. Additionally, regular meetings, email updates, or online forums will serve as platforms for communication and sharing ideas. The leadership team will aim to foster a more cohesive and effective academic community through these strategies.

Addressing Performance Gap

The performance gap analysis identified the primary issues impeding optimal performance as a notable lack of collaborative efforts, insufficient support from full-time faculty, and the absence of structured mentoring models (see Appendix A for further details). To address these root causes, an intervention and solution strategy was developed, central to which was a robust mentoring model. This model aimed to foster and institutionalize a culture of support and collaboration among faculty members. Danaei (2019) highlighted the effectiveness of peer mentoring in providing comprehensive support through regular mentor-mentee interactions, training sessions, and access to institutional resources tailored explicitly to part-time faculty's unique needs. The goal was to establish a structured framework in which experienced, full-time faculty members could offer guidance, support, and share knowledge with part-time faculty, thus bridging the gap in support from full-time faculty.

To foster collaboration, the mentoring model introduced mechanisms for joint projects and research endeavors between mentors and mentees, aiming to cultivate teamwork and

dissolve barriers between full-time and part-time faculty. Williams et al. (2022) highlighted the importance of mentorship relationships between these groups to enhance collaboration and educational quality. By engaging in projects, faculty members can learn from each other, exchange diverse perspectives, and cultivate a unified and cooperative community. The AIP mentoring model accommodated various mentoring styles and needs, ensuring effectiveness and responsiveness to part-time faculty's requirements. Regular feedback sessions were integrated to allow continuous improvement and relevance of the mentoring process. Additionally, professional development workshops, seminars, and informal meet-ups were included, providing opportunities for part-time faculty to develop new skills, stay updated on best practices, and build stronger networks within the academic community, empowering them and promoting a culture of continuous learning and development.

Overall, by implementing this comprehensive mentoring model, the intervention directly addressed the root causes of the performance gap, creating an environment where collaborative work was the norm, support from full-time faculty was readily available, and effective mentoring relationships could thrive, thereby enhancing faculty members' overall performance and satisfaction.

Action

After several meetings with stakeholders, discussing root causes and the possible interventions and solutions, the following steps as mentioned in the implementation plan were utilized in the AIP:

Develop the Intervention

A mentoring program for part-time faculty members was developed based on a thorough needs assessment. This program aimed to pair part-time faculty members with full-time faculty

mentors, providing them with guidance and support to navigate their roles successfully. The program was designed to tackle the challenges highlighted during the needs assessment. Mentor Training (refer to Appendix D) was developed to prepare mentors for their roles, and an online resource center for mentors and mentees was established. The development of the mentoring program was led by the researcher with the assistance of the mentoring committee.

Identify the Participant Group

The AIP's participant group comprised part-time and full-time faculty members who expressed interest in the mentoring program. The initiative was divided into two activities: a Mentor Training session for full-time faculty and mentoring sessions for part-time faculty. Participation in the program was voluntary, with participants selected based on their interests and expertise related to the Problem of Practice. Department chairs collaborated with full-time faculty to identify and recruit potential mentors for the program. Both mentors and mentees completed the Informed Consent process (see Appendix E) before initiating. It is crucial to note that mentor participants did not play a role in the mentoring program's implementation. Their involvement was crucial for evaluating the mentor training's effectiveness. The researcher took on the mentor role for the mentee participants, establishing a suitable mentor-mentee match.

Conduct End of Training Survey (mentor participants)

Feedback on the mentoring program's effectiveness was solicited from the mentor participant group. This survey was conducted at various project stages to ensure the program adequately met the faculty's needs. The researcher used the feedback to make necessary corrections and improvements to the program. The department chairs and the mentoring committee assisted the researcher in gathering the surveys.

Implement the Intervention

The mentoring program was rolled out once fully developed, and the participants were identified. The implementation phase spanned five weeks, during which the mentor initiated the process with an Initial Interview and continued to document observations in the Implementation Journal.

Collect Data

Data collection was an ongoing process throughout the implementation of the mentoring program, aimed at evaluating its effectiveness. This involved gathering participant feedback, conducting surveys, and analyzing performance data to identify areas for improvement. In collaboration with the mentoring committee, the researcher collected and analyzed this data.

Evaluate the Intervention

Following the conclusion of the implementation phase of the mentoring program, and once all relevant data had been meticulously gathered, a comprehensive evaluation of the program's effectiveness was undertaken. This critical step entailed a detailed analysis of the collected data, aiming to assess the impact and outcomes of the program. This analysis gained insights regarding areas of success and aspects that required refinement or adjustment. The objective was to identify opportunities for enhancement to guarantee the program's ongoing effectiveness and relevance. To accomplish this, approximately four weeks were dedicated to the evaluation process. During this time, participant feedback was also considered, ensuring a holistic view of the program's performance and its influence on mentors and mentees. Based on the evaluation's findings, strategic adjustments were planned and implemented to optimize the program's structure, content, and delivery for future iterations.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of the applied improvement project was to implement a mentoring model designed to increase the participation of part-time faculty in quarterly faculty meetings and professional development. Currently, there is a problem of practice where only a small number of part-time faculty members actively participate in these meetings, which take place at various levels such as departmental, divisional, and college wide. The root causes of this problem were identified as a lack of collaborative work, support from full-time faculty, and mentoring models (see Appendix A). Part-time faculty often faced challenges in collaborative work due to their limited availability and fragmented schedules. This resulted in a decreased participation rate in quarterly faculty meetings, where collaboration and sharing of ideas are essential.

In addition, there are concerns raised by some part-time faculty who felt excluded or unsupported by their full-time counterparts, resulting in their hesitancy to actively participate in quarterly faculty meetings (part-time faculty, informal conversation, January 31, 2023). The lack of mentorship and guidance from experienced full-time faculty members hinders their successful integration into the academic community. SCC has implemented support systems and informal mentoring programs to support part-time faculty member's professional growth and facilitate their integration into the faculty team. However, the absence of structured mentoring programs leaves part-time faculty with limited resources and guidance to navigate their various challenges. Therefore, this project addresses these underlying issues by establishing a mentoring model that fosters a more inclusive and collaborative environment that acknowledges and values the contributions of all faculty members, irrespective of their employment status.

Review of the Literature

This literature review delves into the critical issue of limited institutional support and recognition for part-time faculty, which significantly affects the cohesion and effectiveness of academic institutions. It aims to thoroughly explore this problem and identify potential solutions by organizing and synthesizing existing research, theories, and case studies on faculty engagement and support mechanisms. At the heart of this review is the Mentorship Theory, positing that structured mentorship can significantly boost the professional development and satisfaction of faculty members, with a particular focus on those in part-time roles. A meticulous library search was conducted to amass a wide array of scholarly materials that discuss the challenges part-time faculty face, the implementation and outcomes of mentorship programs, and the broader institutional strategies for faculty support. Viewing these issues through the collected works, the review applies mentorship theory principles to part-time faculty's unique context, suggesting it as an effective strategy for enhancing their institutional integration and recognition. Ultimately, this section lays the foundation for a deeper understanding of the complexities of part-time faculty support and positions mentorship as a viable pathway to creating a more inclusive and supportive academic environment, backed by a comprehensive critique and synthesis of the literature.

Overview of the Literature Review

This literature review offers an extensive examination of the aspects surrounding mentorship concerning part-time faculty within colleges and universities. Part-time faculty members encounter challenges such as limited support, restricted access to resources, and fewer opportunities for professional growth. The subsequent section highlights the theoretical

foundations and the implementation of mentoring programs to support part-time faculty and address these specific circumstances.

Problem of Practice and Background

The problem of practice in the Southeastern Community College is the low participation of part-time faculty in quarterly faculty meetings. This lack of involvement can negatively affect the quality of education and the overall functioning of the institution. Despite the administrative team's efforts to support and encourage part-time faculty to participate in meetings, there remains a performance gap between the desired outcomes and the current reality models (see Appendix A). The expected results include increased participation and a sense of belonging from part-time faculty. However, part-time faculty often report feeling disconnected from their institution and lacking the support they need to succeed, leading to lower participation and decreased productivity. According to data provided by the Dean of the Department, an average of 86% of part-time faculty do not attend department, division, and college-wide team meetings based on the most recent meeting attendance models (see Appendix C). The literature review will explore the theoretical factors contributing to this performance gap and identify effective strategies for addressing it through mentoring programs.

Purpose and Organization of the Literature Review

The Applied Improvement Project bonds the performance gap between the desired outcomes and the current reality. The project will follow the Applied Improvement Project Model, which provides an approach to planning, implementing, and evaluating the organizational issue through continuous improvement. The literature review plays a critical role in the AIP, comprehensively analyzing the factors contributing to the performance gap among part-time

faculty. The findings from the literature review inform the development of strategies to address the identified issues and improve outcomes for part-time faculty.

Library Search Process

A comprehensive search was conducted using multiple library systems to achieve this literature review. Peer-reviewed journals were searched using Summon, a Capella Library system, and the SCC College database and library system. Both library systems were linked to Google Scholar to broaden the search. Only peer-reviewed full-text articles published within the last five years were included in the search. Advanced search options were used to include keywords such as (a) mentoring, (b) job satisfaction, (c) professional development, (d) adjuncts, (e) part-time instructors, (f) faculty mentoring, and (g) encouraging adjuncts. The search yielded many articles screened for relevance based on their titles, abstracts, and keywords. The two emerging themes identified were effective mentoring and mentoring structures. These themes will be used to guide the analysis and organization of the literature review.

Theoretical Foundation for the Applied Improvement Project

The mentorship theory is a critical foundation for the intervention proposed in this AIP. Kram (1983) discussed the mentorship theory, initially developed in education. Kram's (1983) seminal work identified three categories of mentoring functions: career-related, psychological, and role-model functions. These functions support mentees and are relevant to this project's goal of addressing the low participation of part-time faculty in team meetings and college-wide activities. Mentoring part-time faculty is an effective strategy for improving employee engagement and participation. By providing part-time faculty with the support, guidance, and resources they need, mentoring can help address the factors contributing to the performance gap and improve outcomes. Mentoring theory offers a framework for understanding and identifying

effective program implementation strategies. The AIP can recommend a supportive and inclusive environment for all faculty members by utilizing the potential of mentoring, leading to improved outcomes for the institution.

The Mentorship Theory

The framework of mentorship theory defines a connection between a mentor and a mentee, where a supportive relationship is established between an experienced and less experienced individual. McDaniel (2020) traced the mentorship theory back to Malcolm Knowles' adult learning principles. McDaniel (2020) discussed Knowles' adult learning principles concerning adult motivation and guidance. Although Knowles did not specifically focus on mentoring as a theory, his work on andragogy highlights the importance of mentorship and guidance in adult learning. He emphasized the significance of self-directed learning in adult learners. Kram (1983) has cited Knowles' work on andragogy to understand the importance of self-directed learning in mentoring relationships. Kram (1983) discussed the theory of mentoring, known as the Relational Model of Mentoring. This model defines mentoring as a developmental relationship where a more experienced mentor provides guidance, support, and feedback to a less experienced mentee. The focus of this model is on the development of a close, personal relationship between the mentor and mentee. It emphasizes the importance of the mentor and mentee working together to achieve the mentee's goals rather than the mentor simply providing advice or direction.

Applications of the Theory of Mentorship

This section explores the practical applications of mentorship theory in various settings. The articles presented in this section identify how the theory guides their studies and discuss its practical applications. The benefits of mentorship programs for part-time instructors, the role of

mentorship in encouraging part-time faculty to become vested in the institution, and the impact of mentorship on the career development of business professionals will be examined. By exploring the applications of the mentorship theory, readers can gain a deeper understanding of its importance in professional development and growth. The practical applications of the mentorship theory involve implementing mentoring programs in organizations to support and guide individuals in personal and professional development. Knowles (2020) provided an example of practical applications of mentorship theory and the benefits of implementing a formal mentoring program for part-time clinical nursing instructors. The mentoring program effectively improved the quality of teaching, increased job satisfaction and retention rates, and built a consistent and stable teaching team. Utilizing a theoretical framework can guide a program's development and implementation stages. The theoretical concepts or expectations that were confirmed include the importance of mentorship in improving the quality of teaching and increasing job satisfaction and retention rates among part-time clinical nursing instructors.

Participation in mentoring programs in higher education has significant value for US college and university faculty. Etzkorn and Braddock (2020) investigated the importance of mentoring relationships in US higher education and their implications for tenure. The researchers have found that mentoring relationships are crucial for faculty members' careers and their success in the tenure process. However, many faculty members do not have access to formal mentoring programs or do not receive adequate support from their mentors. Institutions should provide more support for mentoring relationships, including training for mentors and mentees. They should consider implementing formal mentoring programs to ensure that all faculty members have access to mentoring support. Besides career development for the tenure process, mentoring programs have effectively promoted supportive efforts and job satisfaction among

part-time faculty. Morton and Gil (2019) investigated the effectiveness of co-constructed peer mentoring in promoting professional development and job satisfaction among early-career faculty members. The researchers showed that co-constructed peer mentoring effectively demonstrated emotional and professional support, collaboration and networking, and was intended to enhance job satisfaction and confidence among early-career educational leadership faculty members. The benefits of this model are consistent with the theoretical concepts highlighted concerning the mentorship theory designed by Dr. Kathy Kram.

Mentoring relationships in higher education are pervasive but must be functional. Fitzgerald and McNamara's (2021) found that successful mentoring relationships in higher education are characterized by mutual respect, trust, and open communication. The study also confirmed the importance of matchmaking in mentoring relationships. Theoretical concepts related to mentoring and coaching, such as social learning theory, self-efficacy theory, and transformational leadership theory, were applied to understand the nature of mentoring relationships and the factors contributing to successful mentoring. Fitzgerald and McNamara (2021) suggested implementing a formal mentoring model for part-time faculty members to increase their participation in quarterly faculty meetings and provide personal and professional growth opportunities. Traditional mentoring models have been successful in many educational institutions, but improper implementation can lead to unsuccessful outcomes. O'Hara et al. (2020) found that the mentoring program for secondary novice teachers failed to provide the necessary training to instruct ELLs in academic language effectively. As a result, mentees did not feel prepared to teach language at the end of their mentoring relationships. Mentors also struggled to balance direct, explicit academic language instruction and immersive language instruction for their ELLs. These findings emphasize the importance of proper implementation

and training in mentoring programs to ensure successful outcomes. Proper implementation and training in mentoring programs require a clear understanding of mentoring roles. O'Hara et al. (2020) applied theoretical mentoring concepts to identify the weaknesses and effectiveness of a failed mentoring program. Inexperienced mentors who did not understand their roles were among the identified deficiencies. As Fitzgerald and McNamara (2021) recommended, mentors must ensure they fully understand their specific mentoring job. The mentoring coordinator is responsible for creating successful matches based on knowledge and field of study. Etzkorn and Braddock (2020) emphasized that mentoring must be a developmental relationship where a mentor with experience offers guidance to a mentee with less experience. Therefore, professional mentors must understand their roles and engage in mentoring training to ensure successful outcomes.

Similarities in Theory Application

The articles share many similarities in their results and findings. Firstly, the researchers of all the studies found that mentoring is an effective way to support early-career faculty members. The studies demonstrated that mentoring could provide various benefits, including increased job satisfaction, improved performance, and enhanced career development. Etzkorn and Braddock (2020) confirm that mentoring produces career and psychosocial benefits. Career benefits may occur by helping mentees develop new skills, gain knowledge and insights, and expand their professional networks. Some psychological benefits are increased self-confidence, improved communication skills, and a sense of belonging. Secondly, the studies highlighted the importance of mentor-mentee compatibility and the need for a good fit between mentors and mentees—for instance, Mentor-mentee compatibility is a crucial factor in successful mentoring relationships. It can lead to a productive and effective mentoring relationship. Thirdly, the

studies emphasized the importance of defining specific goals and expectations for the mentoring relationship. This finding suggests that mentoring relationships are more likely to be successful when the mentor and mentee clearly understand what they hope to achieve through the association. Not having a clear understanding can result in a lack of preparedness and unsuccessful mentoring. Lastly, the studies highlighted the importance of ongoing support and feedback throughout the mentoring relationship. It suggests that mentoring relationships are more likely to be successful when mentors provide regular feedback and support to their mentees and when mentees feel comfortable asking for help and guidance. In addition, Fitzgerald and McNamara (2021) emphasized the importance of open communication and sharing experiences to build a strong relationship between the mentor and mentee. This action can help to establish trust and create a supportive environment where the mentee feels comfortable seeking guidance and feedback from their mentor.

Differences in Theory Application

The five studies above applied the mentorship theory and provided similar findings to guiding early career faculty members but utilized theoretical assumptions, concepts, and constructs differently. Knowles (2020) used the theoretical constructs of social learning theory and self-efficacy theory to develop a mentoring program for part-time clinical nursing adjunct faculty. Kram (1983) applied the theoretical constructs of social exchange theory and role theory to establish a mentoring program focused on career and psychosocial benefits. Morton and Gil (2019) used the theoretical constructs of social learning theory and self-determination theory to develop a co-constructed mentoring strategy emphasizing the importance of shared decision-making and goal setting. Fitzgerald and McNamara (2021) applied the theoretical constructs of

social learning theory and self-determination theory to develop a mentoring program focused on mentoring dyads' benefits.

The theoretical assumptions, concepts, and constructs applied in the studies mentioned above are different variables and components of the mentorship theory. As described by Kaplan (2021), the variables help to explain how mentoring works and what factors contribute to its effectiveness. For example, social learning theory is a variable that is commonly applied in mentoring research. Regarding mentoring, the social learning theory proposes that mentees can succeed by observing their mentor's actions and adapting their strategies accordingly. Self-efficacy theory is another variable that is commonly applied in mentoring research. This theory suggests that individuals' beliefs about their ability to succeed in a particular task or situation can impact their performance. Additional variables commonly applied in mentoring research are social exchange and role theories. The social exchange theory proposes that mentors and mentees engage in a mutually beneficial relationship that provides both parties with benefits. The role theory suggests that individuals' roles and expectations can impact their behavior and interactions with others.

Review of the Literature Related to the Problem of Practice

This literature review includes published studies related to the problem of low participation rates of part-time faculty in quarterly faculty meetings. The studies have been clustered based on similarities in examining a similar organizational performance gap. The findings of these studies confirm the need for interventions and solutions to address the challenges part-time faculty face in accessing institutional support and the limited opportunities for collaboration. The studies identified as relevant to the problem of practice have examined the challenges faced by part-time faculty in collaborating in quarterly faculty meetings and proposed

interventions and solutions to address these challenges. For example, Buch et al. (2023) and Luna (2018) have explored the barriers that prevent adjunct faculty from engaging in meaningful collaboration with their colleagues and accessing institutional support. Some of the studies, such as Danaei (2019), Efstathiou et al. (2018), Luna (2018), Perry and Parikh (2017), and Waljee et al. (2020), have focused on the impact of mentoring programs, virtual faculty learning communities, and online mentoring programs on the teaching practices of part-time faculty. Other studies, such as Ran and Sanders (2020), have examined the effects of part-time faculty on student academic outcomes. The studies' findings agree with and confirm the needs assessment by highlighting the need for institutions to provide better support, guidance, and mentorship programs for part-time faculty to improve their effectiveness in the classroom and encourage their participation in quarterly faculty meetings. They also identified similar interventions to the needs assessments, such as implementing mentoring models, encouraging full-time faculty to support part-time faculty, creating a database or online center focused on part-time faculty, and promoting collaborative work.

This literature review highlights the challenges faced by part-time faculty participating in quarterly faculty meetings and explores interventions and solutions proposed in other studies to address this issue. The review identifies the barriers that prevent adjunct faculty from engaging in meaningful collaboration with their colleagues and accessing institutional support and recognition. By examining the findings of these studies, the review seeks to identify strategies that can be used to support adjunct faculty and improve their teaching practices, collaboration, and professional development. The goal is to provide recommendations to help institutions create a more inclusive and supportive environment for part-time faculty.

The peer-reviewed studies have been clustered based on similarities and identified two themes. The first theme is the lack of institutional support and recognition for part-time faculty. In their research, Danaei (2019), Norman et al. (2020), Luna (2018), Buch et al. (2023), and Brennan and Magness (2018). highlight the challenges part-time faculty face in accessing institutional support and recognition, which can lead part-time faculty to feelings of isolation and marginalization. This lack of participation in college meetings can further exacerbate the feelings of isolation and marginalization experienced by part-time faculty. Therefore, institutions must recognize and address these challenges to create a more supportive environment for faculty members.

The second theme is the need for guidance and mentorship for part-time faculty, which includes the studies of Efstathiou et al. (2018), Perry and Parikh (2017), Lunsford et al. (2018), Ran and Sanders (2020), and Waljee et al. (2020). Providing guidance and mentorship programs for part-time faculty can help them better understand the institutional culture and expectations, leading to improved teaching effectiveness and campus knowledge. These programs can also help part-time faculty develop a connection to the institution, improving their job satisfaction and retention rates. By investing in mentoring part-time faculty, institutions can create a more supportive and inclusive environment that benefits part-time full-time faculty and students.

By clustering the studies into themes, this literature review provides an understanding of part-time faculty members' challenges in collaborating in quarterly faculty meetings. The literature review highlights the various factors contributing to these challenges, such as limited time and resources, lack of institutional support, and isolation and disconnection from the institution. By identifying these factors, the literature review makes the need for institutions to take proactive steps to support part-time faculty and create a more inclusive and supportive

environment. These steps include providing mentorship and professional development opportunities and leveraging technology to facilitate collaboration.

Lack of Institutional Support and Recognition for Part-time Faculty

The lack of institutional support and recognition for part-time faculty is a problem of practice addressed by the key studies under the first common theme. Danaei's (2019) analysis focuses on the perspectives of adjunct faculty, often overlooked in research on higher education, and proposes a mentoring program to address the issue. The study demonstrates the program's benefits, including orientation, training, and ongoing support for adjunct faculty. The strengths include its practical solution to address the lack of support for adjunct faculty and its focus on the experiences of adjunct faculty. However, the weaknesses include its limited scope, as it only examines experiences encountered by adjunct faculty at a particular community college, and its reliance on self-reported data from adjunct faculty, which may be subject to bias. Despite these limitations, the study sheds light on the problem of practice by highlighting the lack of support for adjunct faculty and their significant role in educating undergraduate students. It is noted that adjunct faculty are typically excluded from research on higher education institutions, which is consistent with the perspectives of Norman et al. (2020), Luna (2018), and Brennan and Magness (2018). These studies also propose solutions to address the lack of support for part-time faculty.

Mentoring programs have been a common intervention to address the lack of institutional support and recognition for part-time faculty. For example, Danaei (2019) proposed a mentoring program to provide adjunct faculty with the support needed to deliver quality instruction and foster a commitment to the college. The study's findings suggest no challenges or barriers to implementing the mentoring program. However, the study's methodology and conclusions are limited by its focus on a single community college. Although there will be several similar

methodologies from different institutions in this review, future research could examine the effectiveness of mentoring programs for adjunct faculty in diverse institutional contexts to strengthen the study. While there are many limitations, the study illuminates the experiences of adjunct faculty. It proposes a practical solution to address the inadequate support for adjunct faculty in SCC.

Lack of support may also be limited to professional development opportunities and communication. Norman et al. (2020) proposes a comprehensive framework for addressing the needs of part-time faculty in educational institutions, which includes strategies for professional development, mentoring, and communication with college officials. Luna's (2018) study also proposes a framework for addressing the needs of online adjunct faculty in higher education, which includes strategies for professional development, mentoring, and communication with college officials. Luna's (2018) study focuses specifically on the needs of online adjunct faculty. In contrast, Norman et al.'s (2020) study centers on the requirements of part-time faculty in distributed work environments, including distance learning. They provide a solid, comprehensive framework that provides valuable insights to help solve the problem of practice at SCC. Their strategies propose to identify practical approaches to improve the issue of low part-time faculty participation in faculty meetings.

Similarly, Norman et al. (2020) identifies the lack of support for adjunct faculty, particularly in terms of professional development, mentoring, and communication with college officials, as a problem of practice. Part-time faculty desire more support from the administrative team, including feedback, course information, and effective communication. The proposed framework is intended to address these needs and provide adjunct faculty with the necessary resources to be successful. It also emphasizes the importance of maintaining accurate faculty

databases and improving communication between adjunct faculty and college officials to increase their sense of commitment. The methodology included collecting survey data on adjunct faculty members' experiences, needs, and challenges in distributed work environments. This methodology can be a starting point for SCC to develop support programs for part-time faculty. By gathering feedback from faculty and staff, the institution can identify the specific needs and challenges faced by the community and create targeted support programs.

Luna's (2018) research highlights the critical issue of insufficient support for part-time faculty, showing its negative impact on student retention and graduation rates. A meta-synthesis was conducted on academic mentoring programs for part-time online faculty, revealing their desire for mentoring relationships that can be facilitated through a dynamic virtual framework. However, these faculty members often face exclusion from key meetings and decisions, worsening their support deficit. Despite focusing solely on online faculty, thus limiting broader applicability, the findings suggest that mentoring programs could effectively address these support challenges. Norman et al. (2020) further support this by offering strategies for the unique challenges faced by adjunct faculty in distributed work environments. Implementing such mentoring programs, especially in settings where online faculty constitute a significant portion, like SCC (25%), presents a viable solution to the support and investment issues facing part-time faculty.

Following the COVID-19 pandemic, there was a significant increase in part-time online faculty. SCC witnessed a notable rise in its online faculty population, underscoring the demand for enhanced virtual support. Buch et al. (2023) delved into these post-pandemic challenges, focusing on the role of a Learning Community in boosting teaching effectiveness and fostering community among adjunct faculty in a virtual setting. The study implemented Faculty Learning

Communities (FLC) for adjunct faculty to promote instructional excellence and peer learning. Through post-surveys from 14 different cohorts, the research confirmed that the FLC notably improved teaching effectiveness and facilitated a sense of community among its interdisciplinary participants. It highlighted the pedagogical advantages of such communities, including increased engagement and the acquisition of new teaching strategies. Virtual learning communities were shown to offer adjunct faculty valuable opportunities to adapt to new teaching modalities, practice with emerging technologies, and enhance their job satisfaction and success. However, the study's focus on a single Learning Community and its limited sample size were identified as constraints, suggesting that broader research might offer further insights into the scalability and applicability of virtual learning communities across diverse educational contexts.

Another issue includes the lack of professional treatment for part-time individuals who are equally academically prepared as full-time tenured individuals. Brennan and Magness (2018) highlight that adjunct faculty members are not treated fairly and are often compared to low-paying professionals. They are often excluded from meaningful course discussions. This exclusion means adjunct faculty members do not have the same professional growth and development opportunities as full-time tenure-track faculty members. It can lead to isolation and a lack of job satisfaction, ultimately impacting the quality of education that adjunct faculty members can provide to their students. Another challenge faced by adjunct faculty is job insecurity. They are often hired on a semester-to-semester basis, which means they have no job security or benefits. It can make it difficult for adjunct faculty members to plan and lead to financial instability. Despite the growing numbers of adjunct faculty, they are typically left out of institutional discussions about teaching and learning. Brennan and Magness's (2018) call for greater inclusion of adjunct faculty in these discussions is an essential step towards providing

more support for these faculty members. Institutional leaders can use the study's findings to develop support programs for adjunct faculty, such as mentoring programs and professional development opportunities. These programs can help address adjunct faculty's challenges, provide the guidance they need to succeed in their roles and provide high-quality education to their students.

In summary, the five studies under the theme of lack of institutional support and recognition for part-time faculty highlighted the challenges faced by adjunct faculty in higher education. These challenges included the lack of institutional support, job insecurity, and exclusion from meaningful discussions about teaching and learning. Each study proposed practical solutions to address these challenges, such as mentoring programs, virtual learning communities, and greater inclusion of adjunct faculty in institutional discussions. These solutions can help adjunct faculty with the necessary assistance to excel in their positions and provide high-quality education to their students. Institutions of higher education need to recognize the value of adjunct faculty and provide them with the support and recognition they deserve.

Institutional Guidance through Mentorship

Institutional guidance through mentorship is a powerful tool to help part-time faculty navigate their academic and professional journeys more confidently and succeed. Efstathiou et al. (2018) assessed the impact of a formal mentoring program on faculty members' career development, job satisfaction, and retention. The problem of practice had some similarities with the issue addressed in this AIP, which is the lack of information, recognition, and perceptions of marginalization among some part-time faculty. The strength lies in its long-term nature, which allows assessing the mentoring program's short-term and long-term benefits. However, the study's weakness is its small sample size. The authors believe formal mentoring programs can

positively impact faculty members' career development, job satisfaction, and retention.

According to the study, mentees reported personal enhancements in their productivity and satisfaction in various aspects and exhibited more outstanding objective accomplishments than the control group. The favorable outcomes of the initial mentorship program seem to endure for several years, and the same areas continue to be a priority for the mentees. The most compatible faculty were then matched to form mentor pairs. The mentoring sessions included regular meetings and formal training sessions over nine months. However, the study did not use a randomized control group, which could have introduced bias into the results. Also, the study did not assess the impact of the mentoring program on faculty members from other departments or institutions. Instead, it suggested that formal mentoring programs can positively impact faculty members' career development, job satisfaction, and retention. The results are essential to the problem of practice in this AIP because they highlight the importance of formal mentoring programs in higher institutions to support faculty members' professional growth and success.

For effective institutional guidance through mentorship to take place, it is crucial to establish successful mentor-mentee relationships. Perry and Parikh (2017) conducted a qualitative study on developing effective mentor-mentee relationships in radiology. The results of the study pinpoint the key components contributing to successful mentor-mentee relationships in radiology and guide mentors and mentees in establishing and maintaining effective relationships. Like Efstathiou et al. (2018), the study identified the problem of practice as the lack of effective mentor-mentee relationships in radiology. The study's strength lies in its qualitative approach, which allowed for an in-depth exploration of the factors contributing to successful mentor-mentee relationships. According to the authors, successful mentoring models hinge on the alignment of mentees with compatible mentors. Influential mentors exhibit altruism,

honesty, active listening abilities, a collaborative mindset, and approachability. Effective mentees, on the other hand, are characterized by their respect for mentors' guidance and time, active listening skills, and willingness to accept feedback. To nurture strong mentor-mentee relationships, it is crucial to carefully match mentors and mentees, uphold confidentiality, establish clear expectations, promote voluntary participation, and provide the option for mentees to switch mentors without facing criticism or consequences. The study's weakness is its small sample size, limiting its findings' generalizability. They only included radiologists, which may determine the applicability of its results to other fields. Additionally, the study did not assess the impact of the mentoring program on crucial components of this AIP, such as career development and success of the mentees.

The qualitative approach allowed for an in-depth exploration of the factors contributing to successful mentor-mentee relationships. The findings provide important information about the characteristics of influential mentors and mentees and strategies for establishing and maintaining effective relationships. However, the small sample size limits the generalizability of its findings. The study only included radiologists, which may determine the applicability of its results to other fields. Additionally, there was no assessment of the impact of the mentoring program on the career development and success of the mentees. However, the findings provide valuable guidance for mentors and mentees on establishing and maintaining adequate support for faculty members' professional development. Further research is needed to assess the impact of the mentoring program on the career development and success of the mentees and to determine the generalizability of its findings to other fields.

The problem of practice identifies how the lack of guidance impacts the performance of part-time faculty. Ran and Sanders' (2020) study identified the problem of practice as the lack of

guidance and mentoring for part-time faculty, resulting in reduced classroom effectiveness, weak advising, and a lack of curricular cohesion. The weaknesses include the study's limited scope, focusing only on six educational institutions. Additionally, the authors did not explore the reasons behind the lack of guidance and mentoring for part-time faculty. Part-time faculty had less institutional knowledge regarding academic and nonacademic services, which could negatively impact the quality of education throughout higher education. The findings highlight the need for guidance and mentoring for part-time faculty to enhance their classroom effectiveness, curricular cohesion, and advising skills. It recommends that community colleges establish formal mentoring programs to support their part-time faculty's professional development and success.

Technology is crucial in addressing the challenge of insufficient mentorship, particularly for millennials who seek relationships that align with their expectations for frequent feedback and technology-based communication. Studies by Norman et al. (2020), Luna (2018), and Waljee et al. (2020) all underscore the significant impact of technology on mentoring relationships. Waljee et al. (2020) highlight millennials' difficulties in forming effective mentoring relationships, pointing out their unique preferences that traditional mentoring methods often fail to satisfy. This mismatch can lead to frustration and stress, suggesting a need for institutions to evolve their mentoring approaches to cater to the distinct needs of younger generations. To bridge this gap, Waljee et al. (2020) propose innovative solutions like micro-mentoring, which provides rapid and frequent feedback, and reverse mentoring, which fosters a more collaborative and diverse mentorship environment. Additionally, forming mentorship teams can offer multifaceted support and guidance. These strategies emphasize the importance of

adapting mentorship programs to be more flexible and technology-oriented, catering specifically to the needs of part-time faculty in higher education.

Moreover, part-time faculty may face challenges related to a lack of institutional support and recognition, like millennials in other fields. They may not have access to the same resources and opportunities as full-time faculty, hindering their professional development and success. Therefore, institutions should recognize and support part-time faculty's unique needs and preferences in mentoring relationships and adapt their mentoring programs accordingly. By doing so, institutions can help to promote the success and advancement of part-time faculty in higher education. Effective mentoring programs can provide institutional guidance and support to faculty members and help them address the challenges they face in their professional development.

Institutional guidance through mentorship is a crucial aspect of professional development for faculty members. The five studies addressed in this theme highlight the importance of effective mentor-mentee relationships in higher education and the challenges faculty members face in finding mentors who can relate to their experiences and research interests. The studies provide valuable insights into the characteristics of influential mentors and mentees, strategies for establishing and maintaining effective relationships, and the impact of the quality of mentoring relationships on job satisfaction. However, further research is needed to explore specific strategies for addressing the identified challenges and examine the experiences of underrepresented minority faculty with mentoring in different contexts. The studies emphasize the need for more support for faculty members in finding mentors who can guide them through their professional development and help them overcome challenges.

Critique and Synthesis

The literature review highlights critical challenges in faculty mentorship, particularly the insufficient support for part-time, adjunct, and online faculty members who lack access to vital resources and guidance. Moreover, there's a notable gap in mentorship for underrepresented minority faculty, with a scarcity of mentors who share similar experiences and research interests. Addressing these issues is crucial for fostering an inclusive and supportive academic environment. Institutions are urged to prioritize mentorship programs, ensuring all faculty members receive the necessary support and resources for their professional development.

Research by Brennan and Magness (2018), Luna (2018), and Norman et al. (2020) underscores a pervasive lack of support and investment in part-time and adjunct faculty within higher education. Brennan and Magness (2018) highlight adjunct faculty's unfair treatment and low compensation, comparing their situation to that of low-wage workers. Luna (2018) recommends establishing mentoring programs for contingent online faculty to tackle this support deficit, noting the adverse effects on student retention and graduation rates. Norman et al. (2020) highlights the gaps in professional development, mentoring, and communication with college officials, revealing adjunct faculty's desire for more administrative support, including feedback and course information. These findings collectively call for higher education institutions to prioritize supporting and investing in part-time and adjunct faculty to enhance their effectiveness and contribute to student success.

Studies by Buch et al. (2023) and Luna (2018) emphasize the unique challenges and isolation experienced by online faculty, especially adjuncts, highlighting a significant need for specialized mentoring and support systems. Buch et al. (2023) propose the creation of Learning Communities to offer adjunct online faculty a sense of belonging, professional development

opportunities, and mentoring to enhance their effectiveness amidst challenges like those presented by the COVID-19 pandemic. Luna (2018) also advocates for mentoring programs tailored for contingent online faculty to address their support and guidance deficits, ensuring their success in teaching roles. Additionally, while Waljee et al. (2020) focus on millennials' mentoring challenges, they underline the broader necessity for institutions to adapt mentoring programs to online faculty's evolving expectations and needs. These findings collectively call for the implementation of specialized mentoring programs to support the unique needs of online faculty, aiming to improve their performance and positively impact student outcomes.

Research by Norman et al. (2020), Danaei (2019), and Lunsford et al. (2018) underscores a critical gap in higher education: the scarcity of full-time faculty mentors for part-time, adjunct, and underrepresented faculty members. Norman et al. (2020) points out the predominantly part-time composition of college faculty, which exacerbates the mentorship void, especially in professional development, mentoring, and college communication. Danaei (2019) suggests a solution through a mentoring program tailored for adjunct faculty lacking the necessary support and guidance to enhance their instructional quality and commitment to their institutions. Lunsford et al. (2018) highlight the challenges faced by underrepresented minority faculty in finding senior mentors who share their experiences and research interests, leading to professional isolation and hindered development. These findings collectively call for a strategic focus on recruiting and retaining full-time faculty mentors to address the needs of part-time, adjunct, and underrepresented faculty members, fostering a more supportive and inclusive academic environment.

In conclusion, the study highlights a significant challenge in higher education: the limited availability of full-time faculty mentors for part-time, adjunct, and underrepresented faculty

members. It recommends improving mentor training, facilitating connections between part-time and adjunct faculty with experienced mentors, and establishing formal mentoring programs catering to faculty's varied needs, including online instructors, millennials, and minorities. Addressing these issues is crucial for enhancing mentorship quality and supporting all faculty members' professional growth and success.

Review of the Literature Related to the Intervention or Solution

The literature review identified potential interventions to address the problem of part-time faculty's low participation in quarterly faculty meetings, including implementing mentoring models, creating a database or online center focused on part-time faculty, and encouraging collaborative work. Several studies were reviewed to explore how they implemented these interventions and solutions. Williams et al. (2022), Ogbuanya (2022), Mackessy et al. (2019), and Gelman et al. (2022) found solutions in creating formal mentoring programs. Aming et al. (2022), McAtee and Huston (2023), Top et al. (2021), and Kumar and Singh (2018) found solutions in creating a database or online centers for part-time faculty members to access resources and support. McDaniel (2020), Bickerstaff and Chavarín (2018), and Snook et al. (2019) investigated the effectiveness of collaborative work between full-time and part-time faculty members. By reviewing these studies, this literature review provides insights into the potential efficacy of these proposed interventions or solutions in addressing the problem of part-time faculty's low participation in faculty team meetings.

Mentoring Approaches

Integrating effective mentoring strategies is essential to boost the engagement of part-time faculty in faculty meetings. Danaei (2019) and Williams et al. (2022) propose fostering mentorship relationships between part-time and full-time faculty to enhance collaboration and

educational quality. These relationships can leverage traditional and peer mentoring methods to provide comprehensive support, including regular mentor-mentee interactions, training sessions, and access to institutional resources tailored to the unique needs of part-time faculty. Ogbuanya (2022) advocated adopting mentoring programs based on Kram's model that would improve job satisfaction and institutional morale, which could encourage retention and professional development. Mackessy et al. (2019) highlight the effectiveness of online mentoring in increasing part-time faculty's participation in meetings, presenting a cost-effective solution to engagement challenges. Gelman et al. (2022) suggest a multifaceted mentoring initiative specifically for part-time social work instructors, emphasizing professional development and community inclusion, which could be adapted to foster excellent attendance and collaboration in faculty meetings. Collectively, these approaches underline the importance of mentoring and enhancing the participation and collaboration of part-time faculty in academic settings.

Virtual Resources

Part-time faculty members provide valuable expertise and contribute to the diversity of higher education institutions, but due to limited resources, they frequently encounter distinctive obstacles. Virtual resources can be an intervention or solution to this problem. Several studies, including Aming et al. (2022), McAtee and Huston (2023), Top et al. (2021), and Kumar and Singh (2018), have explored different facets of virtual resources for part-time faculty. These studies can provide insights into how institutions can support part-time faculty and improve students' education quality.

Effective ongoing communication between adjunct faculty and leadership is crucial for supporting adjunct faculty and ensuring their success. Aming et al. (2022) identified launching an external website for faculty as a solution to the lack of resources necessary for faculty to

understand essential matters of their duties and best practices for teaching. The website can provide resources such as podcasts, newsletters, and quick teaching tips, contributing to the scope of teaching and learning knowledge and allowing a place for faculty members to get additional support during their teaching term(s). This intervention is significant for part-time faculty who typically lack the resources necessary to understand important matters of their duties and best practices for teaching. Institutions can implement an active faculty list that keeps data on active faculty and their use of the faculty resource site to determine the success of the intervention and ensure that adjunct faculty receive the support they need. Virtual resources have successfully addressed the lack of support for part-time faculty. Mackessy et al. (2019) used Groupme to provide part-time faculty with enhanced mentoring opportunities, information on college updates, and meeting invitations. Similarly, McAtee and Huston (2023) created an e-lounge for part-time adjunct faculty in nursing programs. The intervention included implementing an online support model with onboarding, orientation, and mentorship processes. The e-lounge, using the Canvas software, provides 24/7 accessibility to videos, tutorials, course setup, grading, assessments, teaching practices, and program announcements. The researchers of the study collected data regarding the implementation of the intervention and found that the overall retention rate of part-time faculty increased from 64% to 86%, demonstrating the effectiveness of the intervention.

Virtual resources are equally important for ensuring job satisfaction and retaining part-time higher-education faculty members. Utilizing technology enhances communication, support, and collaboration between faculty members. These interventions and solutions can be applied to all part-time faculty programs, regardless of the discipline or institution. By investing in the support and development of their part-time instructors, institutions can ensure their programs'

continued success and their student's academic success. Implementing virtual resources such as McAtee and Huston's (2023) e-lounge can create a more supportive and inclusive environment for all faculty members, ensuring the continued success of their programs. However, not all faculty members can keep up with such resources. Top et al. (2021) explore the preferences of a faculty team in the process of individual technology mentoring. The study emphasizes the significance of individualized technology mentoring for faculty members, both part-time and full-time. Faculty members require more support in learning software programs, designing instructional materials, workload support, and technical assistance.

Therefore, technology mentoring is essential to implementing a virtual lounge, as McAtee and Huston (2023) suggested. By implementing effective technology mentoring programs, institutions can empower their faculty members to integrate technology into their teaching practices, ultimately leading to improved student learning outcomes. Unfortunately, not many studies discuss the importance of utilizing virtual resources as a support system for part-time faculty in higher education, but institutions that implement them understand their value. Kumar and Singh (2018) provide valuable insights into using electronic resources in the library. The study identified the preferred information sources and methods for accessing electronic information among faculty and research scholars, which can inform the design and implementation of electronic resources in the library. The study proposed an intervention or solution that involved improving infrastructure and support to ensure users can access e-resources effectively. Institutions should consider providing technical support, raising awareness about available resources, and offering training programs to improve users' access to electronic resources.

Collaboration

Collaboration is critical to enhancing part-time faculty's teaching skills and integration into academic communities. McDaniel (2020) introduces a three-stage model focusing on seminars, videotaping teaching sessions, and peer review to foster mutual support and instructional improvement. This model is expected to bolster part-time faculty's engagement and effectiveness by facilitating constructive feedback and peer support. Bickerstaff and Chavarín (2018) highlight a project at community colleges that engages part-time faculty in instructional design and student success initiatives, providing them with essential resources and policies to better support students and enhance teaching outcomes. These strategies emphasize the importance of creating strong connections among faculty members to share resources and address teaching challenges, fostering a collaborative and supportive environment. However, institutions often overlook the need for such collaboration, leading to feelings of isolation among part-time faculty, as Snook et al. (2019) noted in their study on sessional faculty in healthcare. The study underscores the necessity for closer collaboration between sessional and tenure-track faculty to acknowledge and leverage the valuable contributions of part-time faculty, ultimately creating a more inclusive and engaging academic community for all faculty members.

Critique and Synthesis

This section will synthesize and critique various interventions and approaches to support part-time faculty, as addressed in the literature review. It will compare practical mentoring methods, virtual resources, and collaborative efforts between part-time and full-time faculty, evaluating their effectiveness and examining issues from diverse viewpoints. The analysis will progress from broad concepts to specific insights, offering a detailed examination of the strengths and weaknesses of these strategies. Furthermore, it will consider these methods'

potential advantages and disadvantages, proposing innovative perspectives for future initiatives. The discussion will be organized around key themes related to interventions and solutions.

Mentoring Approaches. Mentoring programs aimed at supporting part-time faculty have shown success across various models, including Ogbuanya's adaptation of Kram's model, Williams et al.'s peer and faculty mentoring, Mackessy et al.'s online text messaging mentoring, and Gelman et al.'s comprehensive approach integrating professional development, mentoring, and community inclusion. These programs have increased job satisfaction, higher retention rates, enhanced research productivity, career progression, improved self-confidence, better communication, collaboration, and a stronger sense of community among part-time faculty. However, challenges such as the effectiveness of mentoring for specific groups, like female faculty, and the suitability of text messaging for those less comfortable with technology highlight the need for tailored mentoring strategies. The significance of involving faculty in program development, accommodating diverse needs, and employing varied data collection methods to validate mentoring program effectiveness is also emphasized.

Virtual Resources. Virtual resources have significantly supported part-time faculty through various innovative interventions. These include Aming et al.'s (2022) launch of an external website dedicated to best teaching practices, McAtee and Huston's (2023) creation of an e-lounge for faculty interaction, Top et al.'s (2021) personalized technology mentoring, and Kumar and Singh's (2018) exploration of faculty's electronic resource needs and behaviors. These initiatives have enhanced instructional quality and provided valuable insights into faculty information needs. However, challenges such as the suitability of these resources for all faculty members and the potential limitations of virtual spaces in replicating face-to-face support highlight the importance of customizing interventions. Adequate virtual resources should be

developed with faculty input, tailored to their specific needs, and designed for ease of use to ensure broad accessibility and utility.

Collaboration. Collaboration among faculty members is essential for enhancing teaching quality, supporting part-time faculty, and improving student outcomes. Research by McDaniel (2020), Bickerstaff and Chavarín (2018), and Snook et al. (2019) demonstrates various approaches to fostering such collaboration. McDaniel's study advocates for a three-stage model focusing on the collaborative improvement of teaching practices through observation and analysis. Bickerstaff and Chavarín emphasize the importance of part-time faculty collaborating to share resources and address challenges. At the same time, Snook et al. stress the need for closer collaboration between sessional and tenure-track faculty, especially in the healthcare sector. Each study highlights the value of collaboration in offering new perspectives, practical strategies for teaching enhancement, and support mechanisms for part-time faculty, showcasing the multifaceted benefits of faculty cooperation across disciplines and roles.

Review of the Literature Related to Methods

A systematic approach is needed to identify root causes and develop solutions to address the low participation of part-time faculty in team meetings. Lack of support and guidance for part-time faculty is a primary cause, which can be addressed through methodologies of mentoring models, collaboration efforts, and online resources. Mentoring models are adequate, as demonstrated by Etzkorn and Braddock's (2020) introduction of mentoring models that create relationships where experienced faculty provide guidance, support, and feedback to less experienced faculty. Qualitative data collection methods like interviews can help identify the best model for the institution. Meetings with stakeholders throughout the AIP process are crucial to ensure alignment with institution needs and goals and stakeholder involvement in designing

and implementing solutions. The rationale for addressing the low participation of part-time faculty in team meetings is based on a systematic approach that aligns with root causes and solutions. Involving stakeholders throughout the AIP process is critical for success, ensuring all perspectives are considered, and solutions align with the institution's needs and goals. This collaborative approach builds buy-in and support, identifies implementation barriers, and develops strategies to overcome them. The project can create sustainable solutions that benefit the institution by involving stakeholders.

The Applied Improvement Project (AIP) model is a powerful tool for organizations committed to improving the participation of part-time faculty in faculty team meetings. By following the AIP model, researchers can identify and address problems systematically and, in a data-driven manner, continuously improve their processes and outcomes. The AIP model consists of several stages, including generating alternatives for solutions, implementing the action plan, collecting and analyzing data on the effectiveness of the collaboration methods, and evaluating the outcomes. Using a systematic approach, the AIP model can help ensure all potential solutions are considered, and the most effective strategies are implemented, reflected on, and recommended for continuous improvement. This framework guides the first three steps of the AIP model. Step one involves diagnosing the problem through surveys, one-on-one meetings, and interviews with faculty. Step two is creating a data analysis matrix to identify trends and critical factors contributing to the problem. Step three is a collaborative stakeholders' meeting to generate solutions aligned with the institution's needs and goals. The final step is creating an action plan based on stakeholder suggestions and gaining approval before moving to the next phase. Using a structured approach in the AIP ensures systematic and data-driven problem-solving. Involving stakeholders ensures that solutions align with the institution's needs

and goals. The framework guides the first three steps, including diagnosing the problem, identifying key factors, generating solutions, and developing an action plan. This approach builds buy-in and support for the project, which is essential for success.

Using literature to support the AIP is crucial for evidence-based development. This section addresses three areas of interventions: mentoring models, collaboration, and online resources for part-time faculty. Three studies provide insights into the benefits of mentoring, collaboration, and online resources. Lucas and Dandar (2021) emphasize the importance of creating mentoring models for faculty engagement. Eisenschmidt and Oder (2018) explore the role of mentoring in encouraging collaboration and building a collaborative school culture. McAtee and Huston (2023) focus on innovative strategies to enhance adjunct faculty support and retention. These studies provide a solid methodological foundation for the AIP project, which develops effective strategies to support and retain faculty members.

Lucas and Dandar (2021) explored the importance of mentoring in emergency medicine faculty engagement across multiple institutions. They analyzed data from the Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC) StandPoint Faculty Engagement Survey (SFES) from 26 US Liaison Committee on Medical Education (LCME)--accredited medical schools. Using the 5-point Likert scale, the SFES assesses satisfaction and agreement across 15 dimensions of workplace engagement, including mentoring and feedback. The authors used descriptive statistics and chi-squared analyses to analyze differences between subgroups of survey respondents. The American Institutes of Research approved the StandPoint Surveys data collection and research efforts. Lucas and Dandar (2021) analyzed data and accessed aggregated survey responses through their StandPoint Faculty Learning Community membership. They used a cross-sectional design and online survey, finding that nearly 80% of emergency medicine

faculty reported receiving some mentoring, with formal mentoring associated with higher workplace satisfaction and retention rates.

Mentoring part-time faculty can increase engagement and reduce attrition. Emphasizing the importance of mentoring can guide the AIP process in developing effective strategies for mentoring part-time faculty. Lucas and Dandar (2021) can show data collection methods by asking about the frequency and types of mentoring part-time faculty receive workplace satisfaction, and retention rates. This method can help the AIP process address the low participation of part-time faculty in quarterly faculty meetings and create sustainable solutions. The study emphasizes the importance of mentorship continuity for beginning teachers' professional development and collaboration with colleagues. However, it also highlights the need for professional development systems that address part-time faculty's professional issues in advance. Sustainable mentorship can create a solid basis for collaboration among faculty, and enhancing part-time faculty's involvement in college development should attract more attention from senior management.

The authors, both faculty members at Tallinn University of Estonia, conducted the study with participants from an induction program between the University and assigned schools in the Estonian school system. Lucas and Dandar (2021) collected data from teachers who participated in the induction program and had stayed in the profession for five years. Inductive content analysis was used to interpret the answers, and the results showed that teachers became more critical of senior management support and some school context factors. The study used quantitative and qualitative methods, with open-response questions allowing for a deeper exploration of mentoring and collaboration in the school context and can help identify key themes and patterns. This data offers valuable insights into the AIP's designs and methods.

Virtual platforms such as an e-lounge are innovative strategies that can enhance part-time faculty support. McAtee and Huston (2023) developed an adjunct teaching model and proposed the integration of onboarding, orientation, and mentorship processes through an e-lounge platform. The study addressed that these processes support adjunct job satisfaction and retention. The authors used a mixed-methods approach, including a literature review, surveys, and interviews with stakeholders, to evaluate the effectiveness of the e-lounge platform. The steps were to identify the problem, conduct a literature review, engage stakeholders, develop innovative strategies, and assess their effectiveness to use this study as a guide for the AIP design and methods. The study developed an e-lounge model that included onboarding, orientation, mentorship processes, virtual meeting sites, and informational links. The authors used a mixed-methods approach to evaluate the effectiveness of the adjunct teaching model. McAtee and Huston (2023) involved adjunct faculty members in quality improvement efforts through surveys and focus groups. The participants provided cost savings, increased flexibility, and reduced geographic limitations. The results addressed that the e-lounge model could support part-time faculty retention. This data is supported by evidence-based methods that showed the retention rate rose from 64% to 86% after implementing the outlined strategies.

In conclusion, the studies and literature reviewed in this project provide valuable insights that can be used to clarify the design and methods of the AIP project. Following the steps outlined in the studies, the research will help identify the problem or issue, conduct a comprehensive literature review, engage stakeholders, develop innovative strategies, and evaluate their effectiveness. The findings from the studies suggest that adjunct faculty provide significant benefits to institutions, including cost savings, increased flexibility in offering courses, and reduced geographic limitations. Additionally, the studies highlight the effectiveness

of evidence-based methods in encouraging the retention of adjunct faculty members. By incorporating these findings into the AIP's design and processes, the project can develop strategies to support adjunct faculty retention and increase their participation in quarterly faculty meetings and discussions. Furthermore, the literature suggests that engaging stakeholders, including adjunct faculty members, in designing and implementing the AIP can lead to more effective strategies and better outcomes. By involving adjunct faculty members in developing and implementing the AIP, their perspectives and experiences are considered, and the approach is tailored to their needs and preferences.

Literature Review Summary

The proposed interventions in the Academic Improvement Plan (AIP) aim to enhance the mentoring process by incorporating career and psychological support, as highlighted by Etzkorn and Braddock (2020). By adopting mentoring models, establishing an online resource database, and promoting collaborative efforts, the plan seeks to foster a nurturing and inclusive atmosphere. This approach boosts faculty members' job satisfaction, performance, and retention rates. The AIP underscores the necessity for mentors and mentees to acquire specific skills and knowledge through dedicated training, aiming to cultivate more fruitful mentoring relationships. These improved relationships are anticipated to bring significant benefits such as enhanced knowledge sharing, job performance, and satisfaction.

In addition, the literature review within the AIP highlights the critical role of mentoring in adult learning and the substantial advantages of effective mentoring relationships. Furthermore, the theme of collaboration, as addressed in studies by McDaniel (2020), Bickerstaff and Chavarín (2018), and Snook et al. (2019), points out the importance of faculty collaboration in elevating teaching quality, supporting part-time faculty, and improving student outcomes.

These studies collectively advocate for practical strategies like observation through videotaping and analysis and stress the necessity of collaboration for overcoming challenges and fostering professional growth. Other research, including works by Aming et al., McAtee and Huston, Top et al., and Kumar and Singh, focuses on leveraging virtual resources to aid part-time faculty, noting improvements in instructional quality and support. The overarching message from these studies is the critical need for interventions to be tailored to the unique needs of part-time faculty, ensuring that virtual resources are both accessible and effective in enhancing job satisfaction and retention.

Applied Improvement Project Methods

Maxwell's (2013) model for qualitative research design provides a comprehensive framework that can be effectively applied to the overall structure of this Action and Implementation Plan (AIP). The primary objective of this AIP is to enhance part-time faculty participation in meetings and training by implementing a mentoring program. Let's explore how each component of Maxwell's model relates to this AIP:

Goals

The goals component of the AIP involved clearly defining the desired outcomes and impacts of the mentoring program. In this case, a specific goal was to increase the attendance and active participation of part-time faculty in meetings and training, fostering a sense of belonging and engagement within the college community. It is crucial to address the problem of part-time faculty feeling disconnected and not fully engaged in the college community. By investigating the effectiveness of a mentoring model, this AIP sheds light on the issues related to the lack of support for part-time faculty and how it impacts their sense of belonging and participation in college activities. Conducting this study shed light on the potential impact of implementing a

mentoring program and its influence on the practices and policies surrounding part-time faculty support. The results of this study hold significant importance as they can inform decision-making and policy development, creating a supportive environment for part-time faculty, ultimately benefiting the overall college community.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework served as the theoretical foundation for the mentoring program. It involved identifying relevant theories or models that explain the factors influencing faculty participation and engagement. For example, Kram's (1983) seminal work about mentoring identified three categories of mentoring functions: career-related, psychological, and role-model. These studies guided the design and implementation of the mentoring program, ensuring that it is grounded in established theories and best practices. By incorporating such theories and models, the AIP effectively addresses the underlying factors that hinder part-time faculty participation and engagement.

Research Questions

The AIP research questions focus on two fundamental aspects: process-guiding questions and outcome-guiding questions. Process guiding questions delve into the implementation of strategies learned by participants during the mentoring program, as well as the response of part-time faculty to these strategies. The two questions are: how will the participants implement the strategies learned during the mentoring program, and how will the part-time faculty respond to those strategies? Outcome guiding questions explore the perceptions of part-time faculty regarding the implementation of mentoring programs, how mentoring programs contribute to improved outcomes of part-time faculty participation in faculty meetings and the various approaches participants employ to implement the strategies presented during the

mentoring interventions. The three outcome questions are: what are the perceptions of part-time faculty about the implementation of mentoring programs, in what ways did mentoring programs lead to improved outcomes of part-time faculty participation in faculty meetings and professional development, and in what ways are participants implementing the strategies presented during the mentoring interventions? These questions are stated in the intervention component of this study. By formulating precise research questions, the AIP narrowed down the scope of investigation and gathered targeted data to evaluate the effectiveness of the mentoring program.

Methods

The methods component outlines the strategies and activities implemented to increase participation. This method includes designing and implementing the mentoring program, setting up mentor-mentee pairings, conducting surveys or interviews to gather feedback, and analyzing attendance records. These methods play a vital role in assessing the effectiveness of the mentoring program in achieving the desired outcomes. By employing rigorous and systematic approaches, the AIP collected reliable data to evaluate the impact of the mentoring program on part-time faculty participation. The analysis of attendance records and feedback gathered through surveys or interviews provided valuable insights into the program's effectiveness and areas for improvement.

Validity

Maintaining validity was crucial to ensure that the data and findings from the AIP were reliable and accurate. To uphold validity, the AIP considered potential sources of bias or error. One crucial step was to ensure confidentiality in data collection and analysis. The AIP addressed honest and uninhibited feedback, reducing the likelihood of response bias ensuring that participants' responses remain anonymous. Furthermore, the AIP emphasized the use of reliable

measurement tools. By selecting validated instruments or developing robust measurement protocols, the AIP increased the accuracy and consistency of data collection. The increase included using established survey scales, interview guides, and observation protocols previously tested and proven to yield reliable results.

By utilizing Maxwell's model for qualitative research design, this AIP benefited from a well-structured and comprehensive approach. It ensured that the goals were clearly defined, the program was grounded in relevant theories, the research questions were focused, and the methods were robust. This approach enhanced the overall quality and effectiveness of the AIP in increasing part-time faculty participation in meetings and training through implementing a mentoring program.

Participants and Stakeholders

Participant involvement was critical at every stage in the Applied Improvement Project (AIP). Understanding the perspectives of those involved was crucial for the program's effectiveness. This overview details the participants and stakeholders engaged in the intervention, emphasizing their significant contributions. Their efforts were a major factor in the program's success.

Participants

The Applied Improvement Project (AIP) involves three full-time faculty members serving as mentors and two part-time faculty members as their mentees. These individuals participated in the project's activities, including workshops, mentoring sessions, and other professional development opportunities. The selection of the participants considered their enthusiasm for them to contribute to its success. The role of the mentees was to provide feedback on the effectiveness of the intervention or solution. They were requested to share their insights,

opinions, and suggestions for improving the intervention. The mentors guided and supported the mentees throughout the project, ensuring they had the necessary skills and knowledge to contribute effectively. The information gathered from the mentees was utilized to assess the effectiveness of the intervention and adjust, ensuring its continued success. The mentees were an essential part of the AIP, as their feedback helped shape the intervention and ensured that it effectively addressed the Problem of Practice identified by the SCC. By involving both part-time and full-time faculty members, the project fostered a culture of collaboration and ensured that the intervention effectively addressed all faculty members' needs.

Other participants included eight Department Chairs who collaborated in the implementation process and four members of the faculty mentoring committee. These participants were also stakeholder candidates. The size and makeup of the participant group for the Applied Improvement Project (AIP) were carefully considered to ensure that the project effectively addressed the Problem of Practice identified by the SCC. The rationale for the size and makeup of the participant group was as follows:

Size. The participant group for the AIP was limited to a minimum of 4 part-time and full-time faculty members to ensure that the project was manageable and that the participants could be fully engaged in the project's activities. Smaller group sizes also allowed for more in-depth discussions and feedback, which were critical to the success of the intervention.

Makeup. The participant group for the AIP included both part-time and full-time faculty members to ensure that the intervention effectively addressed all faculty members' needs. By involving both groups, the project fostered a culture of collaboration and ensured that the intervention effectively addressed all faculty members' needs.

Expertise. The participant group for the AIP was selected because of their experience and interest in the project. Participants were chosen because they were willing to contribute to the project's success and their expertise in the Problem of Practice identified by the SCC.

Stakeholders

The key stakeholders of the implementation plan included the Dean of the Division, the Department Chair, the Faculty Department Coordinator, and the mentoring committee. The Dean of the Division played a crucial role as the main stakeholder, overseeing the largest division of the institution and making important decisions for the program's success. Demonstrating support, the Dean provided essential data, actively participated in the first stakeholder meeting, and shared valuable literature resources to aid in a successful implementation. The Department Chair was also a primary stakeholder responsible for coordinating and supervising the faculty. With a strong interest in this AIP, her ideas and recommendations were thoroughly discussed in the stakeholders' meeting, making them an integral part of the potential interventions. The Mentoring Committee is an essential organization established by the Dean to provide robust support for the mentoring project. Composed of dedicated full-time and adjunct faculty members who have demonstrated a genuine interest in mentoring, their stakeholder roles encompass many responsibilities. These include actively supporting the development of a comprehensive mentoring program, assisting in the recruitment of both mentors and mentees, offering valuable insights and recommendations for pairing suitable mentor-mentee relationships, providing unwavering support during training and orientation sessions, and actively participating in the evaluation process to ensure the program's effectiveness and success.

Implementation Plan

Table 1 shows the roadmap designed to guide the execution of the essential interventions for the project's success. It outlines the specific tasks associated with each intervention, identifies the team members responsible for executing these tasks, and sets a clear timeline complete with deadlines to ensure timely completion. The plan also specifies the criteria for evidence of completion, providing evidence that each task has been successfully executed. This approach ensures that every phase of the project is carefully planned and executed, with accountability and efficiency at its core.

Table 2

Implementation Plan

ACTIVITY/ INTERVENTION	TASKS	WHO	TIMELINE	DEADLINE	EVIDENCE of COMPLETION (Outputs)
Initial meeting to discuss the implementation of the action plan	Prepare clear goals for the implementation and identify tasks.	Mentoring committee and primary stakeholders.	July 10 – September 15	September 15, 2023	Completed.
	Identify or create mentoring workshops for future mentors	Researcher	July 10 – September 15	September 15, 2023	Completed and shared in the facilitator guide.
Meet with the department chair to explain the mentoring process.	Assign mentoring coordinators and identify full-time mentoring candidates and part-time mentees.	Department Chair	October 9 – 14	October 14, 2023	Completed and shared in the AIP journal
Mentors will participate in mentoring training (see facilitator's guide).		Mentoring committee and mentor candidates	October 16 - 21	October 21, 2023	Completed and data has been collected (surveys)

Develop an online mentor resource center.	Create mentor resources, checklists, evaluation forms, and a list of collaboration suggestions.	Mentoring Committee	July 10 – September 15	September 15, 2023	Completed and evidence has been shared in the facilitator guide (see appendix D).
Develop an online mentee resource center.	Create mentee resources, things to know, and where to find.	Mentoring Committee	July 10 – September 15	September 15, 2023	Completed and evidence has been shared in the facilitator guide.
Create mentor-mentee match.		Department Chair.	October 2 - 13	October 21, 2023	Completed
Implement mentoring sessions.		Mentors and mentees	October 16 – November 4	November 4, 2023	Completed and data has been collected (surveys)
Data Collection and Analysis	Collect evaluation forms.	Edwin	Nov 6 - 11	November 11, 2023	

Table 2 provides a comprehensive implementation plan that outlines the various interventions, associated tasks, timeline, and corresponding deadlines. This table serves as a visual representation of the structured approach adopted for executing the plan effectively. Each intervention is identified, and the specific tasks are detailed for its implementation. The timeline indicates the planned sequence of activities, while the corresponding deadlines highlight the expected completion dates for each task. This implementation plan is a valuable tool for tracking progress, ensuring timely completion of each intervention, and facilitating effective project management. Table 2 is a valuable resource for project stakeholders to overview the implementation process and ensure smooth execution comprehensively.

Guiding/Evaluation Questions

To effectively evaluate the effectiveness and impact of mentoring programs, utilizing a set of guiding questions as valuable tools for planning and implementing the project is essential.

This section focuses on two fundamental aspects: process-guiding questions and outcome-guiding questions. Process guiding questions delve into the implementation of strategies learned by participants during the mentoring program, as well as the response of part-time faculty to these strategies. On the other hand, outcome guiding questions explore the perceptions of part-time faculty regarding the implementation of mentoring programs, how mentoring programs contribute to improved outcomes of part-time faculty participation in faculty meetings, and the various approaches participants employ to implement the strategies presented during the mentoring interventions. Ultimately, the utilization of guiding questions ensured the success of a project by providing a clear roadmap for implementation and evaluation.

Process Guiding Questions

- How will the participants implement the strategies learned during the mentoring program?
- How will the part-time faculty respond to those strategies?

Outcome Guiding Questions

- What are the perceptions of part-time faculty about the implementation of mentoring programs?
- In what ways did mentoring programs lead to improved outcomes of part-time faculty participation in quarterly faculty meetings and professional development?
- In what ways are participants implementing the strategies presented during the mentoring interventions?

Data Collection Plan

The detailed data collection process was implemented using a comprehensive approach involving various methods, including an AIP implementation journal, interviews, and surveys. These methods were strategically chosen to gather valuable insights, perspectives, and feedback from both mentor and mentee participants, allowing for a thorough examination of the

effectiveness and impact of the mentoring program. The interviews, referred to as the Initial Interview Transcript, were conducted with the two mentee participants. Through in-depth conversations, these interviews provided the mentees with an opportunity to share their thoughts, challenges, and successes from previous mentoring experiences and express their expectations for the current program. The AIP implementation journal served as a platform for reflection and documentation of the progress made throughout the implementation stage. It allowed the researcher to record experiences and track their development over time. On the other hand, surveys provided a structured method of data collection, enabling a broader understanding of the program's outcomes and identifying areas for improvement. Three different surveys were utilized in this project. The Mentor Training Evaluation gathered input from mentor candidates regarding the training and resources provided by the mentoring program. The mentee participants completed the Mentor Evaluation Form at the end of the mentoring process to gather their feedback. The mentors conducted the End of Mentoring Survey to assess the process and outcomes of the program from their perspective. By employing these diverse data collection techniques, the AIP ensured a comprehensive assessment that enriched the understanding of the program's impact on participants and provided guidance for future enhancements. For more detailed information about the data collection plan, please refer to Table 3, which gives a complete overview of the guiding questions and data collection types.

Table 3

Data Collection Plan

Guiding Question(s)	Type of Data to be Collected	Data Source	When Collected	P, O, PO
How will the participants implement the strategies learned during the mentoring program?	Initial Interview with Mentees. Survey Questions	Mentor Training Evaluation Initial Interview Transcript Mentor Evaluation Form	After the intervention	P

How will the part-time faculty respond to those strategies?	One-on-one mentoring Progress Notes	Implementation Journal Mentor Evaluation Form	After the intervention	P
What are the perceptions of part-time faculty about the implementation of mentoring programs?	Initial Interview Survey Questions Observations and Progress Notes	Initial Interview Transcript Mentor Evaluation Form Implementation Journal	After the intervention	O
In what ways did mentoring programs lead to improved outcomes of part-time faculty participation in quarterly faculty meetings and professional development?	Survey Questions Observation and Progress Notes Participation Attendance to Meetings	End of Mentoring Survey Mentor Evaluation Form Implementation Journal	After the intervention	O
In what ways are participants implementing the strategies presented during the mentoring interventions?	Survey Questions Observation and Progress Notes Participation Attendance to Meetings	End of mentoring survey Mentor Evaluation Form Implementation Journal	After the intervention	O

Note: P stands for Process, O stands for Outcomes.

Table 3 serves as a detailed data collection plan, providing a clear framework for gathering essential information related to the project. The table categorizes the data collection process into guiding questions and identifies the corresponding data sources. This way, organizing the data collection plan ensures that all relevant aspects are covered, and the data collected aligns with the project's objectives. The table highlights explicitly that process and outcome data will be collected after the intervention, emphasizing the importance of evaluating the effectiveness and impact of the implemented strategies. Appendix C provides further details on the specific data sources used for the collection, offering transparency and accessibility to project stakeholders.

Qualitative Data Collection Instruments

The qualitative data collected in the Applied Improvement Project played a crucial role in understanding the implementation process and the project's outcomes. Five data sources were utilized: the AIP Implementation Journal, Initial Interview Transcripts, Mentor Training Evaluation, Mentor Evaluation Form, and End of Mentoring Survey (See appendix C). These data sources provided valuable insights into the project's strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement. The data was collected through various methods, which are shown in the following sections:

AIP Implementation Journal. Keeping a journal proved to be a highly effective method for collecting reflections and data in the entire implementation process. The applied researcher utilized a journal to carefully document experiences, reflections, and valuable insights about their mentoring relationships. This journal was thoughtfully organized into daily entries, with numerous notes included throughout the process. It served as a comprehensive record of the mentoring program's goals and objectives, the progress made towards achieving them, and any challenges or obstacles encountered. The applied researcher utilized the journal to carefully document interactions with mentees, including the topics discussed, the feedback provided, and the outcomes of these discussions. This journal served as an invaluable resource, providing a wealth of data to evaluate the effectiveness of the mentoring program and identify areas where improvements could be made. As such, the mentoring program gathered invaluable insights that greatly informed future program development and implementation.

Initial Interview Transcript. One-on-one sessions were conducted with two mentee participants using a reliable video conferencing platform to ensure a comprehensive interview. The interviewer adhered to an interview protocol, posing relevant questions and delving deeper

when necessary to gather detailed information. The interviews, although concise, focused on crucial aspects such as the participants' expectations from a mentoring program, whether they had prior experience with such programs, and how they envisioned the mentoring interventions benefiting them personally and professionally. These inquiries provide mentors with a solid understanding of the participants' expectations, serving as a strong starting point for initiating effective mentoring interventions. The conversation was transcribed at the end of the interviews, and themes were identified. The results will serve as a valuable foundation for the AIP, offering insights into the participants' needs, preferences, aspirations, and possibilities for enhancing the mentoring experience.

Interview Questions

1. Have you ever participated in a mentoring program?
2. What are your expectations from a mentoring program?

Mentor Training Evaluation. A questionnaire was designed for mentor participants to gather feedback on the mentoring training process. After the mentor training tutorial, mentors were requested to complete the questionnaire using an online survey tool. Upon completion of the training the participants received a survey link. Participants were given a two-week deadline to ensure a timely response. The responses collected through the online survey website were organized into tables for further examination, facilitating a comprehensive analysis of the feedback provided by mentors. The following questions were asked:

Questions – Mentor Training Evaluation

1. In what ways can a mentoring program positively impact your personal and professional development?

2. Share specific examples of how the mentoring program can help you overcome challenges or obstacles in your career?
3. If you participated in a mentoring program, did you notice any improvements in your skills, knowledge, or job performance? How did the mentoring program contribute to your overall job satisfaction and engagement?
4. Would you recommend a mentoring program to new faculty? Why or why not?
How likely would you become a mentor?
5. How likely would you use the resources presented in this tutorial with your mentee?
6. How likely would you encourage your mentee to participate in professional development opportunities?
7. How likely would you encourage your mentee to participate in future faculty meetings?
8. How likely would you participate in collaboration efforts with your mentee?

Mentor Evaluation Form. A questionnaire was distributed to capture the mentoring experience from the mentees' perspective. This survey incorporated a blend of closed-ended and open-ended questions. An online survey website was employed to ensure the confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents, fostering an environment conducive to honest and unbiased responses. The responses were collected in the last mentoring session. The collected responses were systematically organized into tables, enabling a thorough data analysis. The questionnaires were effectively distributed to mentees, eliciting their valuable insights on the process and outcomes of the mentoring program. The following section shows each survey question.

Questions -Mentor Evaluation Form

1. How did your mentor assist you in understanding the division's administrative processes?
2. How did your mentor assist you in understanding the institution's administrative processes?

3. How did your mentor assist you in understanding the discipline's administrative processes?
4. What collaboration efforts did you or plan to do with your mentor or other colleagues resulting from the mentoring program?
5. How often did you participate in faculty team meetings before participating in the mentoring program?
6. Do you plan to attend the next faculty team meeting? Explain your reason.
7. Before having a mentor, how often did you participate in professional development offered by the institution?
8. Do you plan to participate in future professional development opportunities offered by the institution?
9. The mentoring program was beneficial for me.
10. My mentor was accessible.
11. My mentor communicated regularly.
12. My mentor assisted me with preparing for teaching by understanding where to find resources and materials.
13. My mentor assisted me in how to create my coursework, syllabus, reports, post-grades, and other additional teaching support offered on campus.
14. My mentor assisted me with understanding the college community regarding atmosphere, philosophy, community involvement, norms, and campus cultural diversity.
15. My mentor demonstrated interest in my learning process.
16. My mentor was professional.
17. For future questions, I will contact my mentor.
18. My mentor was an asset to my learning process as a new instructor.

End of Mentoring Survey. A questionnaire was distributed to mentors to gather feedback on the overall mentoring experience with mentees. This survey consisted of both closed-ended and open-ended questions. An online survey website was utilized to streamline the data collection process. The responses received from mentors were collated and organized into tables, facilitating in-depth analysis. The questionnaire was completed by mentors, capturing their unique perspectives on the process and outcomes of the mentoring program. The subsequent section showcases each survey question.

Questions – End of Mentoring Survey

1. How often did you meet with your mentee?
2. How would you describe your mentee's learning progress?
3. Mention one significant learning experience the mentee gained from the mentoring process.
4. Mention one significant learning experience you gained from the mentoring process.
5. How did you encourage collaboration efforts between part-time and full-time faculty members, and how has it impacted on the work environment?
6. Please list all collaboration activities completed as part of the mentoring process.
7. What was your most beneficial collaboration or development activity with your mentee?
8. What was the most challenging part of the mentoring process?
9. How did you encourage your mentee to participate in faculty team meetings?
10. Did you encourage your mentee to participate in professional development opportunities?
11. How did you become a faculty mentor?
12. How can the faculty mentoring program improve?
13. Would you repeat the process with a new mentee?
14. If the answer is yes, is there anything you would do differently? Please explain briefly.

Quantitative Data Collection Instrument

A quantitative data collection instrument did not apply to this intervention plan.

Data Analysis Plan

The data analysis plan in this study was a crucial component that outlines the systematic approach to analyzing and interpreting the collected data. Table 4 presents a robust data analysis plan developed to gain meaningful insights and draw accurate conclusions from the data gathered through various methods such as AIP implementation journals, interviews, and surveys. This plan involved organizing, coding, and categorizing the data to identify patterns, themes, and trends. The data analysis plan ensured a rigorous and systematic approach to derive meaningful conclusions, make informed decisions, and inform future improvements in the AIP.

Table 4

Data Analysis Plan

Type of Data	Analysis Procedures/Plan
AIP Implementation Journals	Data is prepared for analysis by organizing entries into a digital format, such as a Word document. Labels and themes coded entries and then analyzed to identify trends and patterns. Deidentification occurred to protect privacy. The digital format of the journals was stored on a secure server/ cloud-based platform with restricted access.
Initial Interview Transcript	Data was prepared for analysis by transcribing the interviews into a digital format, such as a Word document. Labels and themes coded entries and then analyzed to identify trends and patterns. Deidentification occurred to protect privacy. The transcripts' video recordings and digital formats were stored in a secure server/cloud-based platform with restricted access.
Mentor Training Evaluation	Survey results were prepared for analysis by organizing entries into tables using a Word document. Labels and themes coded entries and then analyzed to identify trends and patterns. The digital format of the surveys was stored on a secure server/ cloud-based platform with restricted access.
Mentor Evaluation Form	Survey results were prepared for analysis by organizing entries into tables using a Word document.

<p>End of Mentoring Survey</p>	<p>Labels and themes coded entries and then analyzed to identify trends and patterns. The digital format of the surveys was stored on a secure server/ cloud-based platform with restricted access.</p> <p>Survey results were prepared for analysis by organizing entries into tables using a Word document. Labels and themes coded entries and then analyzed to identify trends and patterns. The digital format of the surveys was stored on a secure server/ cloud-based platform with restricted access.</p>
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Table 4 presents the data analysis plan, outlining the specific types of data that will be collected and the corresponding analysis procedures. This table provides a clear framework for organizing and processing the collected data to derive meaningful insights. The data types to be analyzed include the AIP implementation journal, initial interview transcript, mentor training evaluation, mentor evaluation form, and end-of-mentoring survey. The results from these data sources, detailed in Appendix C, offer a comprehensive range of information to assess the effectiveness and impact of the mentoring program. The analysis procedures will depend on the nature of the data collected, such as qualitative analysis for interview transcripts and thematic analysis of open-ended survey responses. By delineating the types of data and the appropriate analysis procedures, Table 3 ensures a systematic and rigorous approach to data analysis, enabling project stakeholders to draw valid conclusions and make informed decisions based on the findings.

Detailed Qualitative Data Analysis Plan

A series of comprehensive steps were undertaken to analyze the qualitative data effectively. As Creswell and Creswell (2018) recommended, qualitative data were collected through interviews, journals, and focus groups. Table 4 provides a detailed plan outlining the analysis of data gathered from the AIP Implementation Journal, Initial Interview, Mentor Training Evaluation, Mentor Evaluation Form, and End of Mentoring Surveys. Thematic

analysis was employed as the primary approach for examining the data. This analysis involved transcribing the data and meticulously identifying significant emerging themes and patterns. The coding process required multiple data readings to identify recurring themes and patterns, which were then thoughtfully organized into relevant categories and subcategories. The coded data was subjected to thorough analysis to determine prevalent patterns and themes, including assessing the frequency of codes and patterns across the entire dataset.

Furthermore, comparisons were made across different data sources to identify commonalities and distinctions. Subsequently, the data was interpreted to draw meaningful conclusions about the mentoring program, including addressing the process and outcome questions. All components were securely stored on a server or cloud-based platform with restricted access to ensure data security. Additional measures, such as password protection, were implemented to safeguard against unauthorized access. Regular data backups were performed to mitigate potential loss during system failures or unforeseen circumstances. The data will be stored for a specified period and subsequently securely deleted or destroyed in compliance with data protection regulations. Moreover, any identifying information will be removed during the analysis process to protect the interviewees' privacy.

Limitations

The implementation of mentoring strategies to boost the participation of part-time faculty in team meetings was carefully designed with a focus on addressing the study's limitations, ensuring validity, and upholding ethical standards. The limitations faced included the availability of resources, the willingness of participants to engage with the mentoring program, and the possibility of unforeseen circumstances that could affect the study's outcomes. To accurately gauge the impact of the mentoring program on part-time faculty's involvement in team meetings,

maintaining the study's validity was deemed essential. Maxwell (2013) emphasizes the importance of anticipating potential limitations and devising strategies to minimize their effects, thereby enhancing the integrity and validity of the research findings. In parallel, ethical considerations were prioritized to safeguard participants' privacy throughout the study. This section delves into these critical aspects—limitations, validity, and ethics—and examines their collective influence on the execution and results of the mentoring program, highlighting the thoughtful approach taken in its implementation.

Throughout the process of implementing the mentoring program, several potential weaknesses warrant attention. The availability of resources emerged as a significant concern, notably the allocation of funding and time, which directly influenced both the program's execution and its sustainability. Specifically, a lack of sufficient funds for mentor and mentee support and training could have compromised the program's capacity to enhance part-time faculty attendance at team meetings. Moreover, the effectiveness of the intervention was potentially at risk due to the varying levels of participants' engagement. A notable portion of part-time faculty might not have shown interest in the program or recognized the importance of participating in team meetings, thereby challenging the achievement of the program's objectives. Additionally, scheduling conflicts represented another barrier that could limit faculty participation, highlighting the complexity of factors affecting the program's success.

Addressing challenges to maintain the study's validity, credibility, and dependability presented its hurdles. One significant challenge was the risk of selection bias, which could emerge if the participant pool wasn't fully representative of the broader part-time faculty population. This situation was a particularly tough challenge, given the study's focus on part-time faculty members who opted into the mentoring program, potentially skewing the sample.

Additionally, the Hawthorne effect threatened the study's validity, as participants might have modified their behavior or responses knowing they were under observation. This effect was virtually unavoidable, as the nature of the mentoring program implementation made participant awareness of the study a given.

Further complicating matters was the issue of data reliability, including the potential for survey questions to lack clarity. It was challenging to manage, especially given the study's limited duration. Moreover, the type of data collected was inherently tied to the specific research question and the methods employed for data management, adding another layer of complexity to ensuring validity. The accuracy of participants' responses also posed a risk; there was a concern that individuals might not provide honest feedback if they felt it could lead to judgment or negative evaluation. These challenges underscored the intricate balance required to minimize threats to the study's integrity while navigating the practical limitations inherent in such research endeavors.

Credibility, Dependability, and Transferability

A range of strategies were carefully implemented to guarantee the credibility, dependability, and transferability of the mentoring program. Credibility, crucial to establishing trust in the program, was ensured through a thorough review by mentoring and coaching experts. This review confirmed that the program was firmly rooted in evidence-based practices and best strategies. Additionally, measures were implemented to enhance the program's dependability, including using qualitative approaches. The program fostered clarity and alignment by establishing goals and sharing them with stakeholders. Standardized procedures were also implemented to maximize effectiveness and ensure consistent outcomes. The mentoring program was intentionally designed to be adaptable to various organizations and contexts, recognizing the

importance of transferability. These comprehensive strategies have successfully created a mentoring program that is credible, dependable, and transferable, thus guaranteeing its effectiveness and success in diverse settings.

Credibility

Several strategies were implemented to ensure the credibility of the action plan and deliver a successful mentoring program. First, the mentoring program was reviewed by experts in mentoring and coaching to provide feedback and ensure that it was based on best practices and evidence-based strategies. As Maxwell (2013) mentioned, validity could be proven through evidence, emphasizing the importance of using robust and validated techniques. Involving stakeholders, mentors, mentees, and program administrators in the development and implementation process ensured that their additions and recommendations were considered. The program was tested with a small group of mentors and mentees to identify and address any issues or challenges before full implementation. In their research, Bourdeaux and Schoenack (2016) utilized two universities to gain insights into the variations and commonalities in experiences and perspectives, enhancing the credibility of their study. Similarly, this action plan benefited from selecting participants from different departments within the division to ensure a more comprehensive and representative view of the results.

Mentors receive training and continuous support to ensure credibility through effective mentoring and equip them with the necessary skills and knowledge. This process enabled mentors to guide and support their mentees effectively throughout their mentoring relationship. By investing in mentor training and ongoing support, the institution enhanced the quality of the mentoring program and increased the likelihood of positive outcomes for mentors and mentees. The mentoring program included an evaluation phase to assess its effectiveness. Lastly,

transparently communicating the mentoring program and its implementation to stakeholders- built trust and ensured credibility.

Dependability

Several strategies were implemented to ensure the dependability of the action plan to deliver a successful mentoring program. Understanding both quantitative and qualitative research approaches, as emphasized by Stringer (2014), was essential for researchers to ensure reliability. After gaining an understanding, it was crucial to establish goals for the mentoring program and communicate them to all stakeholders. This gain provided clarity and alignment, ensuring everyone understood their roles and what needed improvement. Implementing this strategy increased the likelihood of success in reaching desired outcomes, as Maxwell (2013) highlighted. Another dependability strategy was to establish standardized procedures for the program. Danaei (2019) found that implementing standardized processes, including data collection, analysis, and reporting, enhanced the effectiveness of a mentoring program for adjunct faculty members. Dependability and improved support for mentors and mentees were maintained by following standardized procedures.

Documentation of all aspects of the mentoring program was also crucial to ensure dependability. This action included keeping records of mentor and mentee intervention documents, training materials, and evaluation results. By documenting these aspects, the program could be replicated and improved upon in the future. Regular communication between mentors, mentees, and program administrators was essential. The communication ensured that everyone understood and could address any issues promptly. Bourdeaux and Schoenack (2016) emphasized the importance of communication in their research on mentoring experiences, highlighting that effective communication contributed to the success of mentoring relationships.

Finally, continuous evaluation and improvement of the mentoring program based on stakeholder feedback and data collected during the program were necessary. By continuously improving the program, organizations could enhance the quality of mentoring and increase the likelihood of positive outcomes for mentors and mentees. By implementing these strategies, the mentoring program was dependable and successful in achieving its objectives, as supported by the cited research.

Transferability

Just as Kram (1983) ensured transferability with her relational mentoring model, where a more experienced mentor supported a less experienced mentee, the mentoring design used for this study could be adapted to different organizations and contexts. It was essential to have a transferability plan in place to ensure that the mentoring design could be utilized in other contexts. For example, the initial implementation phase started in one department but eventually became transferable to other departments within the division. Involving stakeholders from different departments was crucial to plan a mentoring design that met the needs of the entire division. By collaborating and working together, best practices were shared, and the program was adapted to different contexts. Additionally, providing training and ongoing support to organizations adopting the program was crucial to provide them with knowledge and skills for effective implementation. Lastly, evaluating the mentoring program in different contexts helped assess its effectiveness and identify areas for improvement, ultimately refining the program and making it more transferable.

In terms of transferability in research studies, Maxwell (2013) proposed several measures to maximize trust and application in different contexts. These measures included employing a clear and concise research design, ensuring a diverse sample representing the studied population,

providing a detailed description of the study context, and thoroughly explaining the research procedures. Implementing these measures enhanced the transferability of research findings, making them more applicable in various contexts and populations.

Ethical and Regulatory Issues

The Institutional Review Board (IRB) approves research protocols involving human subjects. Their approval in this AIP was required to ensure that research interventions did not include experimenting with human subjects. This approval was necessary for both Capella University and Southeastern Community College. They acted as guardians through their rigorous review and approval process, ensuring that research interventions involving human subjects are conducted ethically and with utmost care. However, mentoring is an educational and professional development initiative. A clear and convincing argument and supporting documentation helped demonstrate this to the IRB.

While mentoring offers significant benefits, it is crucial to acknowledge the potential ethical and regulatory issues and risks that may impact participants. Common problems include inappropriate behavior, power imbalances, lack of compatibility, and breaches of confidentiality. Unacceptable behavior may manifest when mentors violate professional boundaries, engage in harassment, or discriminate against mentees, creating an uncomfortable or unsafe environment. As noted by Creswell and Creswell (2018), researchers must actively avoid power imbalances and ensure fair treatment of all participants. Establishing clear guidelines and a code of conduct for mentors and mentees is essential to mitigate these risks. Conducting training sessions to educate participants on appropriate behavior, professional boundaries, and reporting mechanisms for concerns is crucial. Power imbalances are often present in mentoring relationships, with mentors typically more experienced and influential. This dynamic can lead to the misuse of

authority or manipulation of mentees. Encouraging mentees to voice their concerns, providing support mechanisms, and regularly monitoring the mentoring relationships can help identify and address potential issues.

Additionally, there is a risk of compatibility lack between mentors and mentees, which can result in ineffective mentoring and dissatisfaction for both parties. O'Hara et al. (2020) highlighted that mismatched personalities, conflicting objectives, or communication styles can impede the effectiveness of the mentoring relationship. To mitigate this risk, a careful matching process should be implemented, considering the mentors' and mentees' goals, interests, and personalities. Regular check-ins and evaluations should be conducted to assess compatibility and effectiveness, allowing for necessary adjustments or reassignments. Finally, confidentiality breaches pose a significant risk as participants may share sensitive or confidential information during the mentoring process. Maxwell (2013) stressed the importance of handling such information carefully to protect participants' privacy. Clear policies and guidelines should be established regarding confidentiality, emphasizing the importance of maintaining trust. Mentors should be trained in handling confidential information appropriately, and mechanisms for reporting breaches should be in place.

SECTION 2. IMPLEMENTATION

The successful implementation of the mentorship program heavily relied on process analysis and data collection. This section exposes the essential process and data analysis required for the effective execution of the AIP. The initial phase involved a thorough breakdown of the various stages of the mentoring process, enabling the identification of strengths and areas for improvement. The data was collected through surveys and interview transcripts to gain valuable insights into mentor training needs and mentee perspectives. By analyzing this data, the researcher can evaluate the program's effectiveness, identify significant trends, and make well-informed decisions to enhance the program.

Process Analysis

The AIP data collection and analysis process progressed steadily with mentor training and mentoring implementation. The implementation consisted of two sections - training for future mentors and a mentoring process utilizing two mentee participants. The researcher actively participated in the mentor training and took on the role of a mentor for this study. An AIP implementation journal was used to monitor and document the implementation. Following the mentor training, mentor participants were given a mentor training evaluation survey to gather their insights and ideas about guiding a mentoring relationship effectively. This feedback was valuable in refining the mentor training program for future iterations.

The Mentoring Process

Before the mentoring interventions began, the two mentee participants were interviewed to gain insight into their perspectives on mentoring and expectations. These interviews provided valuable insights into the mentees' needs and goals. After the implementation, the mentees complete a mentor evaluation form to assess the impact of the mentoring program on their

professional journeys and determine if it provided a solution to the problem of practice. The mentoring interventions were scheduled for five consecutive weeks. Each mentee participant had weekly meetings with their mentor to discuss specific topics. These topics were identified in the first meeting after the interviews, ensuring the mentoring sessions were tailored to the mentees' interests and needs. The participants were given access to a mentoring Canvas course, which provided them with additional mentoring materials and surveys. The mentor created a Microsoft Teams notebook for each participant to facilitate communication and establish contact through the Teams chat platform. These Microsoft Teams notebooks included action plans with specific interventions and topics to be discussed over the five weeks. At the end of week 5, the mentee participants completed mentoring evaluation forms, and the mentor submitted an end-of-mentoring survey.

The mentee participants displayed high engagement and enthusiasm during the mentoring sessions. Their active participation can be attributed to the fact that each session focuses on topics of their choosing, which has kept them motivated and invested in the process. The problem of practice that the mentoring program addresses is the low participation of part-time instructors in faculty team meetings and professional development opportunities. The participants' demonstrated interest in becoming more engaged is a positive indicator that the mentoring program has the potential to provide a solution to this problem. By actively participating and seeking opportunities for growth and development, the mentee participants are taking steps toward increasing their engagement and involvement in the academic community. This progress is encouraging and suggests that the mentoring program is on track to solving the problem of practice positively.

While the implementation has progressed according to schedule, there have been a few setbacks. First, some surveys were not completed on time, including the survey from the second mentee participant. Additionally, the first mentee participant fell ill, requiring rescheduling of the mentoring sessions. However, this adjustment was quickly made and did not cause significant delays. Next, not all survey results from the mentor training have been received. Efforts were made to collect and analyze the remaining survey data to ensure a comprehensive analysis of the entire program. Throughout the mentor training process, the stakeholders provided valuable insights and feedback. Their input proved to be instrumental in improving the mentor training program. They shared tips and suggestions on how to enhance the training, allowing for necessary adjustments to be made to ensure its effectiveness. Fortunately, there have not been any surprises or unanticipated difficulties aside from the setbacks mentioned earlier. The implementation has progressed smoothly, staying on track with the original plan. However, one notable change from the initial implementation plan was the lower number of mentor participants than anticipated. While the project initially aimed for eight participants, only three surveys were completed. The analysis will consider this discrepancy to ensure a comprehensive program evaluation.

Assumptions

Several assumptions were made regarding mentor candidates' participation and completion of the training survey. However, due to the nature of the video training, there is no record of the number of participants. Only three surveys were completed, challenging the assumption that many participants would provide feedback. Another assumption was that there would be sufficient time for collaborative opportunities, participation in faculty team meetings, and professional development. However, the reality was that time constraints did not allow these

activities to occur as initially anticipated. These challenges highlight the need to reassess and adjust expectations regarding participant engagement and available time for collaborative activities and professional development. Considering these limitations and appropriate modifications to future implementations is essential to ensure more accurate assumptions and realistic outcomes.

Communication and Data Collection

The intervention was conducted with a strong emphasis on respecting the participants. Clear and transparent communication offered participants a comprehensive understanding of the intervention's purpose, expectations, and potential risks or benefits. They ask questions to ensure their complete comprehension of their involvement in the AIP. Before participating, participants were allowed to provide informed consent. They received all relevant information concerning their roles, responsibilities, and any potential risks or benefits associated with their participation. Their consent was entirely voluntary and could be withdrawn without any adverse consequences. Strict measures were implemented to safeguard participant confidentiality and anonymity. Personal identifying information was kept separate from the collected data, and any data shared or reported was presented in an aggregated and anonymized manner. This manner ensured the protection of participants' privacy and identity, fostering an environment of trust and respect.

Participants were actively encouraged to provide feedback and input throughout the intervention, including their thoughts on the mentoring program, suggestions for improvement, or any concerns they may have had. Their perspectives were highly valued and considered when shaping the intervention and making necessary adjustments. Participants were provided with regular check-ins and support through team meetings and email communication. This action facilitated promptly addressing any questions, concerns, or challenges they encountered during

the intervention. A culture of respect and care for their well-being was fostered by promptly acknowledging and addressing their needs. By implementing these respectful practices in communications and data collection, the intervention demonstrated a firm commitment to treating participants with dignity, protecting their rights and interests, and establishing a positive and supportive environment for their active involvement.

Tools for Mentoring

Participants and members of the organization were provided updates and information about the progress of the implementation through the following actions:

1. **Contact email communication:** Regular email updates were sent out to participants and members, providing them with detailed information about the progress of the implementation. These emails included key milestones, achievements, and any critical updates related to the implementation.
2. **Updates via Teams:** An online collaboration platform like Microsoft Teams was utilized to provide real-time updates and information. The mentors created dedicated channels or groups where participants and members could receive updates, share progress, and discuss any concerns or questions.
3. **Action plan using Microsoft notebook:** A Microsoft notebook created an action plan outlining the implementation process. This notebook served as a central repository of information and progress updates. Participants and members could access this notebook to view the action plan, track progress, and stay informed about the implementation's advancement.
4. **Weekly Zoom meetings:** Weekly Zoom meetings were conducted to provide a more interactive and face-to-face platform for updates and information sharing. Participants

and members could join these meetings to receive updates, discuss progress, address challenges, and provide feedback.

5. Canvas course with mentoring resources: A Canvas course was created specifically for mentors and mentees. This course included resources and information helpful for the mentoring process, such as modules on building effective relationships, goal setting, communication skills, and professional development. Mentors and mentees could access this course to enhance their mentoring skills and find additional support.

Data Analysis

This section gathers information from three different types of participants: mentor candidates, part-time faculty mentees, and assigned mentors. The mentor candidates participated in a test phase of the training session to learn about the designed mentoring program. They did not become mentors during the implementation stage. They were asked to provide feedback about the designed mentoring program to understand the effectiveness and sufficiency of the training in preparing them for a mentoring role.

It is essential to note that the mentor participant in the implementation phase and the researcher are the same person. The part-time faculty members interested in receiving formal mentorship served as mentees. They were assigned to the mentor and participated in a 5-week mentoring process. The mentor conducted an initial meeting and interviewed the mentees to understand their expectations of the mentoring relationship. Together, they created an action plan using a daily planning checklist, guiding their weekly meetings. The mentor documented the process in an implementation journal to gather input. At the end of the five weeks, the mentees were encouraged to complete a mentoring evaluation form to assess the effectiveness of the program and draw conclusions about its potential to address the problem of practice. The

assigned mentor practiced the tasks learned in the mentoring training session. They were responsible for organizing and conducting the mentoring sessions with the mentee participants. They completed an end-of-mentoring survey at the end of the five weeks, which gathered feedback about the mentoring process. The following section presents the process data used and analyzes the mentoring process.

AIP Implementation Journal

The AIP Implementation Journal contained the AIP process and the mentoring sessions by documenting specific behaviors, actions, and indicators observed. This documentation allowed for the quantification and analysis of these observations to identify patterns, trends, and areas needing improvement within the mentoring process. The journal was consistently updated following each session with participants, thus providing a detailed record of the mentoring progression. As noted in the AIP Journal (refer to Appendix C), the initial meeting consisted of an interview to collect vital information and establish a foundation for the mentoring relationship. The following sessions offered continuous support to the mentees, addressing their inquiries and concerns. Table 5 presents data on the mentor's engagement with mentees during these sessions, including discussions on relevant topics and guidance tailored to their needs and interests, organized into the major themes that derived from the initial codes.

Table 5

AIP Implementation Journal Themes

Guiding Question	Initial Codes	Themes	Example Quotes	Count
Process 1	Online mentoring platform Virtual resources	Mentoring Resources	Week 4: A mentoring hub and discipline resources were finalized to provide mentors with the resources required to implement strategies during the mentoring program.	2
Process 2	Virtual resources Teams GroupMe	Effective Communication	Week 6: Communication strategies utilizing Teams were initialized. The mentor training tutorial was completed by participants, providing them with the	2

			necessary tools to implement the strategies they learned.	2
Process 2	Fulltime colleagues Administration	Support	Week 7 - 9: Participants met with a mentor to receive training on student registrations, such as withdrawal procedures, incomplete applications, and grade submissions.	
Process 2	Campus tour Training Session Learning strategies	Professional Development	Week 9: Participants received training about professional development and went on a campus tour. These are all learned strategies expected to be implemented.	2

Table 5 summarizes the data captured in the Implementation Journal, highlighting various aspects of the implementation stage, such as the strategies used, their execution, and the participants' reactions to these strategies. It details how, during intervention meetings, participants expressed interest in attending faculty meetings, participating in professional development opportunities, and gaining a deeper understanding of the college community. The data identified several themes, including mentoring resources, effective communication, support in navigating processes, and professional development. Table 5 analyses this data about process questions, organized by these themes. It is noted that the journal did not capture data related to outcome questions, focusing instead on documenting the implementation process.

Regarding mentoring resources and effective communication, the table emphasizes the foundational efforts of the program, such as establishing a mentoring hub and utilizing Teams for communication. These efforts laid the groundwork for the successful implementation of strategies. Weekly interactions included mentor-led training on student registration processes, withdrawal procedures, incomplete applications, and grade submissions. Additionally, faculty members participated in sessions on administrative tasks and professional development led by the mentor, aiming to incorporate these strategies into their roles seamlessly. A more

comprehensive account of the implementation journey is available in Appendix C, where the complete AIP Implementation Journal is located.

Initial Mentee Interview Transcripts

In the initial meeting, two questions were posed to both participants, and their responses were recorded and transcribed for subsequent analysis. These transcriptions laid the groundwork for theme identification. A code analysis was conducted to determine the primary themes, which informed conclusions about the intervention's effectiveness and the participants' perceptions. The interview themes included effective communication, support, and experiences of lack of support. The interview questions were designed to investigate the participants' expectations of a mentoring program and their previous experiences with such a program.

Table 6

Initial Interview Transcript Data Themes

Guiding Question	Initial Codes	Themes	Example Quotes	Count
Process 1 & 2	Virtual resources Teams GroupMe Fulltime colleagues Administration	Effective Communication /Support	Lines 29 – 34 Participant 1 discusses past experiences with ineffective communication methods. She "hopes to get more of the ins and outs from the mentor program," referring to better communication.	1
Outcome 1	Virtual resources Teams GroupMe	Effective Communication	Line 5 – 12 Participant 2 mentions, "If I have a question, I expect you to clarify my question," emphasizing the need for support when needed.	1
Outcome 1	Fulltime colleagues Administration	Lack of Support	No data about the current mentoring program but referring to past mentoring programs in lines 62 – 70, participant 2 expressed participating in a mentoring program that was not effective.	

Table 6 shows a detailed summary of the data from the Initial Interview Transcript (see Appendix C), intended to understand the participants' expectations of a mentoring program. The analysis focuses on process and outcome data concerning effective communication and the participants' aspirations for guidance and support. Table 6 highlights a participant's desire for

enhanced communication practices, suggesting an openness to adopting new strategies for an improved mentoring experience. Furthermore, the data provided insights into the participants' expectations and illuminated their past negative experiences with mentoring, explaining the impact of these experiences on their views of mentoring programs. This information is vital for tailoring the implementation of strategies to meet the participants' needs and address potential challenges. However, it is essential to note that Table 6 does not detail how the outcomes improved or how participants applied the discussed strategies. The interviews formed a critical component of the Action Implementation Plan (AIP) process, offering valuable insights that guided the next steps in implementation. The complete interviews are available in Appendix C, offering a fuller understanding of the participants' expectations, experiences, and the strategies implemented.

Mentor Training Evaluation

Upon completion of the mentor training, the evaluation phase began with implementing a mentor training evaluation survey. This survey was distributed to the mentor training participants via an online platform, Qualtrics, though only three participants ultimately completed the survey. The survey included open-ended (four questions) and closed-ended (five questions) formats, targeting a diverse group of full-time faculty members. The open-ended questions within the survey yielded qualitative data, which was then subjected to thorough analysis to discern common themes and derive meaningful insights. The analysis revealed three primary themes: professional development, personal development, and networking. To provide a detailed understanding of the participants' feedback, Table 7 outlines the process and guiding questions, accompanied by a summary of the insights obtained. This analysis enriches the understanding of

the mentors' experiences and viewpoints concerning the intervention, offering valuable information for future enhancements.

Table 7

Mentor Training Evaluation Themes

Guiding Question	Initial Codes	Themes	Response Examples	Count
Process 1	Training Session Learning strategies Quarterly meetings	PD/ Faculty Meetings/ Collaboration	Responses 6, 7, and 8: How likely would you encourage participation in professional development, future faculty meetings, and collaboration efforts?	1
			Somewhat unlikely	1
			Somewhat likely	1
			Highly likely	
Process 2	Fulltime colleagues Administration	Support	Response 1: The participants unanimously recognize the program's ability to enhance networking opportunities, fostering growth and expansion in their personal and professional networks of part-time faculty.	3
			Response 2: All participants agree that a mentoring program proves invaluable in overcoming obstacles and challenges by providing guidance, diverse perspectives, and skill enhancement to those seeking help.	3

Table 7 includes organized data collected from the Mentor Training Evaluation, distinguishing between process and outcome data. This survey contains insights on the mentoring program's implementation. The data highlighted in the table mainly pertains to process data, revealing the strategies executed during mentor training. The survey included collected responses from mentors who had completed the training, focusing on their experiences and viewpoints on the strategy implementation.

One question was about the likelihood of encouraging participation in professional development, future faculty meetings, and collaboration efforts. The varied responses indicate a potential need for greater emphasis on these topics in mentor training. Moreover, these responses

appear to diverge from those in the initial section of the survey (refer to Appendix C), suggesting a need for further investigation into any discrepancies. The table also reflects mentor participants' views on the mentoring program's influence on their personal and professional development. Feedback unanimously highlights the program's role in enhancing networking opportunities, thus supporting growth in personal and professional circles. Participants acknowledged the benefits of mentoring in navigating challenges, offering guidance, diverse perspectives, and skill development.

These insights are crucial for understanding the training sessions' effectiveness and impact and assessing the implemented strategies' success. While Table 7 focuses on process data, it is essential to remember that outcome data—detailing the overall results and impact of the mentoring program—is captured using other evaluation tools. These tools offer a fuller picture of the program's outcomes and the participants' experiences. The complete survey results are in Appendix C for a thorough analysis and evaluation.

Mentor Evaluation Form

The mentor evaluation form was critical for collecting feedback and assessing mentors' performance. This form typically consisted of questions or statements enabling mentees to share their views, observations, and ratings regarding their mentoring experiences. The information from these forms was instrumental in evaluating the mentoring program's effectiveness in addressing specific problems, pinpointing areas for improvement, and guiding the development of future mentorship initiatives. As a resource for insight, the evaluation form facilitated a deeper understanding of mentors' contributions from the mentee participants' perspective, playing a vital role in the program's enhancement. Table 8 presents the data derived from eight open-ended and ten closed-ended questions on the form. Analysis of these responses highlighted vital themes

such as support, collaboration, effective communication, faculty meetings, professional development, and mentoring resources, which were identified based on feedback from mentee participants during the program's implementation phase.

Table 8

Mentor Evaluation Form Themes

Guiding Question	Initial Codes	Themes	Response Examples	Count
Process 2	Team Teaching Curriculum Revisions	Collaboration	Participants were interested in participating in future collaboration.	2
Outcome 1	Virtual resources Teams GroupMe Fulltime colleagues Administration	Effective Communication/ Support	The mentor was beneficial, accessible, communicative, prepared, supportive, interested in learning, professional, and overall, an asset to the mentees' learning process – Strongly Agreed	2
Outcome 2	One-on-one meeting Training Session	Professional Development	“Before having a mentor, I had not participated in any professional development opportunities offered by the institution. The mentorship program introduced me to the importance of continuous learning and professional growth”	1
Outcome 2	Quarterly Faculty meetings Division meetings Collegewide Activities	Faculty Meetings	Participant plans to participate in upcoming faculty team meetings. Participant does not plan to participate in upcoming meetings since she is an adjunct faculty and communicates frequently with coworkers.	1
Outcome 3	Online mentoring platform Virtual resources	Mentor Resources	Applied the strategies learned from the sessions to their college journey – Strongly Agreed.	2

Table 8 summarizes the essential data gathered from the Mentor Evaluation Form. This survey evaluated the mentoring program's effectiveness and contained insights into the participants' intentions to apply the strategies discussed. The survey contained outcome data, yielding a thorough understanding of the program's impact and success. It provides insights into

participants' experiences, perceptions, and overall satisfaction with the program organized by themes.

The data regarding the theme of collaboration indicates that participants were interested in future collaborative efforts. The findings highlight the importance of effective communication and support, with participants strongly affirming their mentor's accessibility, regular communication, and assistance in preparing for teaching, including guidance on where to find resources and materials. The mentoring resources made available during the sessions, such as the mentoring hub, were successful in helping create coursework, syllabi, and other teaching supports available on campus. Both participants indicated their commitment to enrolling in professional development (refer to Appendix C). As for future participation in faculty meetings, Table 8 illustrates that one participant intends to join upcoming faculty team meetings, whereas the other, an adjunct faculty member who frequently communicates with colleagues, does not.

This data is instrumental in assessing the implemented strategies' effectiveness and offers critical feedback for enhancing the program. The Mentor Evaluation Form also gathers information on how participants plan to integrate the discussed techniques into their practice. This information is vital for understanding how the strategies are applied and implemented beyond the mentoring sessions. Complete findings from the Mentor Evaluation Form are available in Appendix C for a comprehensive analysis and further data exploration.

End of Mentoring Survey

After the mentoring sessions concluded, the mentor was asked to complete an end-of-mentoring survey. The survey was conducted to assess the outcomes of the mentoring program and gather insights into the participants' commitment to implementing the strategies they learned during the intervention. The survey comprised fourteen open-ended questions to gather

qualitative data about the mentors' overall experience. The mentor completed two surveys, one for each mentee participant. The responses provided by the mentor were carefully examined and analyzed to identify recurring codes and themes and extract valuable insights. The analysis revealed themes such as faculty meetings, collaboration, professional development, and time constraints. This thorough examination of the mentors' responses played a crucial role in understanding their experiences and perspectives regarding the intervention they provided. The analysis results were organized and presented in Table 9, visually representing the findings and providing a deeper insight into the mentors' thoughts and reflections. By reviewing the common themes that emerged from the mentors' responses, a more nuanced understanding of the effectiveness and impact of the intervention was achieved.

Table 9

End of Mentoring Survey Themes

Guiding Question	Initial Codes	Themes	Response Examples	Count 2
Process 1	Training	Professional Development	"I had encouraged the mentee to participate in professional development opportunities and I will be participating with her."	2
Process 1	Team Teaching Curriculum Revisions	Collaboration	"We did not have enough time to do other collaborative activities, but we talked about working together on revamping some of the curriculum content."	2
Process 1	Quarterly Faculty meetings Division meetings Collegewide Activities	Faculty Meeting	"I invited ... to participate and provided her with the steps to request an ASL interpreter for the faculty meetings."	1
			"The mentee is an online instructor so will probably not participate (in quarterly faculty meetings)."	1
Outcome 1,2 & 3	Timeline	Time Constraint	The mentoring program needed "more flexible timeline" to see how participants participated in PD, collaborations and faculty meetings.	2
Outcome 2	One-on-one meeting Training Session	Professional Development	"... was excited to learn more about the resources available to her as an adjunct instructor."	2

Table 9 offers a detailed summary of the information obtained from the End of Mentoring Survey. This table highlights the participants' dedication to implementing the strategies learned during the intervention. It indicates strong encouragement for participation in professional development, with the mentor engaging in professional development sessions and ensuring that the mentee participants would support future opportunities. Although both mentor and mentee acknowledged the lack of sufficient time to carry out activities such as collaboration efforts, there was a mutual agreement to participate in them. Table 9 documents discussions about planning for collaboration efforts identifying time constraints as a critical factor to consider in revising the implementation process. Feedback from mentors and mentees suggests the need for more than the initial four weeks allocated to conduct the mentoring sessions effectively. It is also noted that not all mentor participants were committed to participating in quarterly faculty meetings. Extending the duration of the intervention could yield more accurate and comprehensive data.

The data presented focuses primarily on outcome metrics, offering valuable insights into the mentoring program's effectiveness. The complete results of the End of Mentoring Survey are available in Appendix C for a thorough understanding of the data and to explore participants' responses in depth.

SECTION 3. EVALUATION

In this evaluation section, the report delves into the findings obtained through an extensive evaluation process, focusing on process and outcome questions related to the impact of the mentoring program on part-time faculty. The process questions explore how participants implement the strategies learned during the program and how part-time faculty respond to these strategies. On the other hand, the outcome questions examine the perceptions of part-time faculty regarding the implementation of mentoring programs, the impact on their participation in quarterly faculty meetings and professional development, and the extent to which participants are implementing the strategies learned. The discussion encompasses critiques and implications for professional practices, while recommendations are provided to enhance future mentoring programs. This comprehensive evaluation analysis sheds light on the program's effectiveness, identifies areas for improvement, and offers insights for organizations seeking to implement similar initiatives.

Findings

This section delves into objectively evaluating the mentoring program's effectiveness, focusing on its process and outcome objectives. Through structured inquiries, the analysis explores the implementation of strategies learned during the program by participants and the response of part-time faculty to these strategies. Furthermore, it examines the perceptions of part-time faculty regarding the mentoring program and its impact on enhancing their participation in quarterly faculty meetings and professional development activities. Each question is meticulously analyzed, providing summaries of the main conclusions drawn from the data and juxtaposing these findings with existing literature. By addressing these process and outcome questions, the section presents a comprehensive overview of the mentoring program's

efficacy and its tangible benefits to part-time faculty engagement and professional growth.

Process question 1: How will the participants implement the strategies learned during the mentoring program?

This process was specifically designed for the mentor candidates who participated in the mentoring training. Following their training, they were asked to provide feedback on their learned strategies and how they plan to implement them. The goal was to ensure that the mentors would feel prepared to take on their role and apply the strategies effectively after completing the training. The mentor candidates were not assigned mentees since this was the initial phase of the AIP implementation. They did not participate in the mentoring process with part-time participants in this AIP. Instead, their involvement allowed them to assess the effectiveness of the mentoring training in preparing mentors to provide mentoring. This process also provided valuable feedback on the effectiveness of the training and how these future mentors intend to implement the strategies learned during the program.

The original plan was followed successfully to some extent. However, out of the eight participants invited to complete the mentor training, only three participants completed the training and answered the survey questions. At this point, no modifications were deemed necessary. As indicated in the gap analysis and fishbone diagram (see Appendix A), full-time faculty members are typically occupied with their duties, so fewer participants were expected to complete the training. The main objective of the AIP is to increase the participation of part-time faculty members in quarterly faculty meetings and professional development. However, some unexpected responses and discrepancies in the mentoring training results raised concerns. For instance, in Table 4, questions six through nine focused on how likely the mentor candidates were to use the presented resources with their mentees, encourage mentees to participate in

professional development opportunities, promote mentees to attend future faculty meetings, and collaborate with mentees (See Appendix C). The results indicated that two responses were highly likely, while one response indicated extreme unlikelihood. It is unclear whether the participant who responded extremely unlikely was confused or if they genuinely meant it. Regardless, a re-evaluation of the training's effectiveness will be necessary.

Overall, the participants were actively engaged and provided positive feedback regarding the effectiveness of the training (mentor candidates, email message, October 27, 2023).

According to the survey results, the participants unanimously acknowledged that the program enhanced networking opportunities, fostering personal and professional growth within their networks. They recognized that a formal mentoring program offers valuable opportunities for both learning and networking, allowing them to acquire new knowledge and skills while expanding their professional connections. These findings align with the research of Etzkorn and Braddock (2020), who also emphasized the career and personal development benefits of mentoring. Through mentoring, these benefits help mentees develop new skills, gain knowledge and insights, and expand their professional networks.

Process question 2: How will the part-time faculty respond to those strategies?

The purpose of these guiding questions is to assess the response of part-time faculty toward implementing mentoring strategies. The objective is to evaluate their experience with the mentorship process and determine the effectiveness of the mentoring model. Despite time constraints during the AIP, the timeline was successfully completed. Initially, mentor participants who had completed the training were invited to become mentors. However, due to time limitations, stakeholders recommended that the researcher who designed the mentoring program demonstrate the process with the participants. Two part-time instructors were invited to

participate in the mentoring program, utilizing the specific model developed for this AIP. The mentor conducted an initial interview to understand the participants' needs and explain the program. This action was followed by four consecutive meetings with designated discussion topics and training. The mentor-mentee relationship concluded with an end-of-mentoring survey, although some date modifications were necessary due to conflicts and health issues. Fortunately, these modifications did not impact the overall timeline.

Throughout the course of 5 weeks, regular weekly meetings were conducted. The participants were encouraged to utilize the Microsoft Teams platform to facilitate communication and access to materials. This method of communication played a crucial role in providing regular check-ins. According to Mackessy et al. (2019), utilizing online mentoring platforms like Teams enhances the engagement and participation of part-time faculty in team meetings while also being a cost-effective means of support. This support system effectively communicated important topics and recorded mentoring discussions. Virtual resources were also instrumental in facilitating communication. Since both participants lived far from the campus, using video platforms for one-on-one weekly meetings proved invaluable. Additionally, the Canvas platform provided mentees with a comprehensive list of online resources. Technology integration greatly enhanced the mentor and mentees' communication, support, and collaboration. The satisfaction of the mentees was evident in their survey responses, particularly in questions nine through eleven, which assessed the program's benefits, the accessibility of the mentor, and the provision of resources and materials to enhance understanding. Both participants strongly agreed with these aspects. A similar intervention implemented by McAtee and Huston (2023), which utilized an e-lounge through the Canvas software, resulted in a 64% to 86%

increase in the overall retention rate of part-time faculty, further demonstrating the effectiveness of such interventions.

During the weekly meetings, the mentor discussed various topics with the mentees. The Implementation Journals provide a detailed overview of the weekly activities and topics. These discussions offered the necessary support to the mentees in terms of their teaching process and understanding of the college environment. Additionally, they motivated the mentees to actively participate in future collaboration, faculty discussion meetings, and professional development opportunities. The participants received accurate and relevant information. In fact, during the initial interview, Participant 1 expressed that she had never been aware of the activities offered by the institution and struggled to find guidance. The mentoring sessions effectively addressed this by providing the participants with information about professional development opportunities, collaboration prospects, and invitations to participate in quarterly faculty meetings.

The implementation stage is still in progress, so the study cannot present actual participation results. However, the end-of-mentoring surveys provided insights into participants' willingness to engage in upcoming activities. For instance, in Table 5, Question 4, participants were asked about their readiness to collaborate with their mentor or colleagues. Both participants expressed interest in future collaborations, such as team teaching and curriculum revisions. Participant 2 even shared her prior experience in team teaching and curriculum adaptations, emphasizing her commitment to the department. Several questions in Table 5 focused on quarterly faculty meetings—Question 5 was designed to uncover the reasons behind participants' non-attendance. Participant 1 expressed limited and ineffective participation in quarterly faculty meetings, whereas Participant 2 preferred communicating with the discipline coordinator when

seeking answers. They provided divergent responses when asked about their plans to attend the upcoming faculty meeting. According to Gappa and Leslie (1993), part-time faculty often have additional responsibilities, such as second jobs, limiting their time investment in the institution. Participant 1 demonstrated interest in attending, while Participant 2 stated that frequent communication with co-workers negated the need for her attendance.

In contrast, Questions 7 and 8 revealed that neither participant had previously engaged in any professional development opportunities. However, both expressed a strong desire when asked if they were willing to participate. During the one-on-one meetings, the mentor discussed the benefits of participating in the institution's professional development programs. It became apparent that both participants were unaware of the available opportunities within the institution. This lack of awareness can primarily be attributed to their colleagues' and institutional leaders' lack of support. The fishbone diagram (see Appendix B) also highlights the issue of some part-time faculty being unaware of the professional development offerings provided by the institution.

Outcome question 1: What are the perceptions of part-time faculty about implementing mentoring programs?

This inquiry collects valuable information and perspectives from part-time faculty members regarding their perceptions of mentoring programs. The objective is to delve into their thoughts, opinions, and personal experiences to gain insights into these programs' effectiveness, benefits, and overall impact on their professional development. By comprehending their perspectives, it becomes feasible to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of existing mentoring initiatives and identify potential areas for enhancement. Furthermore, understanding their perception is crucial in determining whether a mentoring program effectively motivates participation in quarterly faculty meetings and fosters ongoing professional development. This

exploration gathers valuable insights to inform the improvement and optimization of mentoring programs for part-time faculty members.

The findings of the improvement project have provided valuable insights into the perceptions of part-time faculty members regarding the implementation of mentoring programs. In-depth interviews conducted as part of the project revealed that mentees place great importance on receiving support and clarification when faced with questions or challenges. These findings highlight the need for adequate support systems within mentoring programs to address mentees' concerns and queries. Interestingly, many part-time faculty members have had previous experience with mentoring, whether in informal or formal settings. Unfortunately, some of these experiences were not positive. During the initial interviews, one participant shared their last encounter with an ineffective mentoring program. This aligns with the findings of O'Hara et al. (2020), who identified various reasons for the failure of mentoring programs, including insufficient training and a lack of preparedness among mentors. The mentees in our study expressed feeling unprepared after their mentoring sessions, emphasizing the importance of proper implementation and training in mentoring programs to ensure successful outcomes. This highlights the significance of including comprehensive training that allows mentors to understand their roles and responsibilities effectively.

Several approaches can be taken to demonstrate the effectiveness and efficacy of a mentoring program and meet the expectations of mentee participants. These approaches include setting clear goals and regularly tracking progress, collecting feedback and evaluations, measuring specific outcomes, gathering mentee testimonials, implementing long-term follow-up, and conducting comparative analysis. Williams et al. (2022) have demonstrated the effectiveness and efficacy of mentoring programs through formal mentoring approaches. These approaches

encompass frequent mentor-mentee meetings, attendance at didactic workshops and training sessions, providing hands-on experiences, feedback from committee members, mentee support groups, and individualized assistance with skill development. By employing these strategies, mentoring programs can gather substantial evidence of their impact on mentees' professional growth and development, ensuring that participants are content and confident in the program's ability to meet their specific needs and goals.

It is essential to recognize that the success of mentoring programs heavily relies on the mentor's training. Providing mentors with the necessary strategies and tools to support mentees effectively plays a critical role in the overall effectiveness and outcomes of the program. This training should equip mentors with the skills and knowledge to guide and empower mentees, fostering a positive and impactful mentoring relationship.

The Mentor Evaluation Form proved invaluable in gaining insights into the mentees' perspective on the mentoring program after completing an entire cycle in the intervention stage. The feedback from both participants strongly indicated that their mentors were highly beneficial, accessible, communicative, prepared, supportive, interested in learning, and demonstrated professionalism. The support provided by their mentors was deemed essential to their overall experience. During the initial interviews, one participant explicitly mentioned their expectations of a mentor, emphasizing the importance of someone who could offer support and clarify any questions. This data highlights mentors' significant role in supporting the mentees' learning process and providing valuable guidance. The positive feedback from the mentees further reinforces the crucial role of mentors in fostering a supportive and conducive learning environment for mentees. The support provided by mentors goes beyond mere guidance and clarification. Mentors also act as a source of motivation and encouragement, helping mentees

navigate challenges and overcome obstacles. Their expertise and experience contribute to the mentees' professional growth and development, ensuring they receive the necessary support and guidance to succeed.

In addition to the support mentors provide, effective communication between mentors and mentees is crucial for establishing a strong and productive mentor-mentee relationship. Open lines of communication allow mentees to express their concerns, seek advice, and receive timely feedback, all contributing to their overall learning experience and professional growth.

Bourdeaux and Schoenack (2016) emphasized the significance of effective communication in mentoring relationships, highlighting its role in fostering understanding, trust, and collaboration. Recognizing this, the mentoring program implemented various strategies to promote effective communication between mentors and mentees. One such strategy was utilizing a mentoring hub and discipline-specific resources, which provided mentors with the tools and resources to communicate strategy and information during the mentoring program effectively. Additionally, communication was facilitated through the Teams platform, which allowed for seamless and efficient communication between mentors and mentees. The positive feedback from mentees regarding their mentors' accessibility and communication skills is a testament to the success of these communication strategies within the mentoring program. Mentees felt their mentors were approachable, responsive, and actively engaged in facilitating effective communication. This indicates that the program effectively addressed the importance of communication by providing mentors with the necessary resources and platforms to effectively engage with their mentees.

When it comes to implementing long-term follow-ups, their importance cannot be overstated. Mentoring is not just a short-term intervention but a transformative journey of growth and development for mentors and mentees. Snook et al. (2019) emphasized that establishing

long-term relationships among faculty members allows for increased collaboration, ultimately leading to improved student learning outcomes. This study highlights the need for ongoing support and guidance after the formal mentoring program ends. The feedback received from mentors in the End of Mentoring Survey further reinforces the significance of extending the duration of the mentoring program. Mentors expressed their belief that the implementation phase of the program was too short, indicating a desire for a longer duration. A more extended mentoring period can potentially enhance the effectiveness and outcomes of the program by providing mentors and mentees with more time to establish a strong rapport, set and achieve goals, and navigate challenges together.

Moreover, mentors and mentees expressed their engagement and eagerness to learn more about the college community. Long-term follow-ups allow for a deeper connection between mentors and mentees, extending beyond the formal program duration. This fosters a sense of continuity and ongoing support, enabling mentors to continue providing guidance, advice, and encouragement even after the mentoring program officially concludes. By maintaining this lasting connection, mentors can continue to serve as valuable resources for mentees as they navigate their academic and professional journeys.

Outcome question 2: In what ways did mentoring programs lead to improved outcomes of part-time faculty participation in quarterly faculty meetings and professional development?

This question seeks to understand the positive impacts and improvements mentoring programs have had on the participation and engagement of part-time faculty members. It determines if formal mentoring is effective in fostering these outcomes. Mentoring programs have been widely recognized as successful strategies for professional development and

improving outcomes across various fields. Kram (1983) acknowledged the positive influence of mentoring on overall career-related and psychological functions. The implemented mentoring program for supporting part-time faculty has yielded remarkable results, providing invaluable guidance, support, and numerous professional development opportunities. As a result, mentees have been empowered to enhance their teaching skills, expand their knowledge, and develop a stronger sense of belonging within the institution. These outcomes have played a crucial role in improving the overall quality of education delivered by part-time faculty members.

Mentoring programs have been identified as a logical solution to improve the outcomes of part-time faculty participation in quarterly faculty meetings. Several studies by Williams et al. (2022), Ogbuanya (2022), Mackessy et al. (2019), and Gelman et al. (2022) support the implementation of formal mentoring programs to increase engagement among part-time faculty in these meetings. However, despite the program's overall success in this AIP, it has not resulted in a clear impact on increasing the participation of part-time faculty in faculty team meetings. This lack of impact is evident in Table 5, where Participant 1 expresses willingness to engage in quarterly faculty meetings. In contrast, participant 2, as an adjunct faculty member, does not see the need for their involvement. These differing perspectives highlight a discrepancy in viewpoints.

Several suggestions can be made to address this disparity. First, the program may have overlooked the specific needs and challenges faced by part-time faculty concerning their participation in team meetings. The AIP Implementation Journal, which provides information about the different topics covered during mentoring sessions, does not give enough attention to the involvement in faculty team meetings. According to the results of the End of Mentoring survey, the mentor was asked how he encouraged the mentees to participate in faculty team

meetings, and the responses showed that the mentor simply extended an invitation to participate in the next faculty meeting. The program's primary focus was on individual professional development, teaching effectiveness, or other areas, with enhancing faculty team meeting involvement as a secondary priority. As a result, the program's impact on this aspect may have been diluted or insufficiently addressed. Secondly, Danaei (2019) suggests that institutions should compensate adjunct faculty fairly to address the lack of participation. Many part-time faculty members are paid based on hourly rates and often teach at multiple institutions to cover their cost of living. This situation may not allow them to allocate time or even have the desire to attend quarterly faculty meetings. While mentoring is highly effective in engaging and investing participants in the institution, it is crucial to address these other factors that hinder the engagement of part-time faculty in quarterly meetings. By addressing compensation concerns and creating a supportive environment that values their contributions, institutions can foster greater participation and involvement in these meetings among part-time faculty members.

Despite initial disinterest from half of the participants in attending quarterly faculty meetings, implementing mentoring interventions was highly effective in fostering professional development opportunities. As noted in the AIP Implementation Journal, participants were introduced to the various professional development offerings available within the institution, which they were unaware of. This newfound awareness sparked their interest in engaging in these opportunities. This observation aligns with the findings of Gappa and Leslie (1993), who emphasize that motivational factors such as personal and professional growth, status, and the potential for a full-time academic position can drive part-time faculty participation.

Mentees received training on the available opportunities to support their professional development further. It is worth noting that prior to the mentoring program, the mentees were

unaware of the institution's provision of professional development resources. However, following the training received from their mentors, both participants expressed their intention to attend future professional development sessions. These outcomes highlight the transformative impact of mentoring interventions in increasing awareness and interest in professional development among part-time faculty and motivating them to pursue such opportunities actively. This underscores the significance of mentoring programs in fostering continuous growth and advancement within the academic community.

Outcome question 3: In what ways are participants implementing the strategies presented during the mentoring interventions?

This question gains insights into how participants implement the strategies presented during the mentoring interventions and assess their effectiveness. By understanding how participants apply these strategies, we can evaluate the impact of the mentoring interventions on their actions and outcomes. The responses to this question will provide valuable information on how participants have integrated the strategies into their practices, including any challenges or successes.

A crucial aspect of the mentoring sessions was providing a list of discussion topics at the outset. This list allowed participants to choose the topics that aligned with their interests and learning goals. Giving participants the autonomy to select the topics they were most interested in fostered a sense of ownership and increased their overall engagement and investment in the mentoring process. This personalized approach ensured that participants were more likely to actively apply the strategies discussed during the mentoring sessions.

While no detailed information is available regarding the specific outcomes of the mentoring interventions, participants expressed their intentions to implement the strategies they

learned in their college journey through survey responses. This demonstrates their commitment to applying the knowledge and skills gained from the mentoring sessions. Their proactive approach toward implementing these strategies indicates a strong desire for personal growth and development. The mentoring interventions fostered a sense of empowerment and relevance by allowing participants to choose their preferred discussion topics and encouraging them to apply the strategies in their college journey. This approach increases the likelihood of participants effectively integrating the techniques into their practices, leading to positive outcomes.

Overall, the mentoring resources, such as the list of discussion topics and the participants' commitment to implementing the strategies, highlight the effectiveness of the mentoring interventions in promoting engagement, ownership, and application of knowledge. This personalized and proactive approach enhances the potential for long-term impact on participants' growth and development.

It would have been beneficial to conduct a follow-up is conducted to evaluate the long-term impact of the mentoring interventions and gather information about the ongoing implementation of the strategies learned. The assessment could have included data on how the participants continued to apply the strategies in their day-to-day practices. Additionally, the evaluation could have explored the participants' level of engagement in faculty meetings and professional development opportunities after the mentoring relationship ended. While both participants expressed differing opinions about their future participation in faculty meetings, they were interested in engaging in professional development activities.

Continued implementation of the strategies and the mentees' participation or non-participation in faculty meetings and professional development opportunities could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the long-term impact of the mentoring interventions. This

information would have provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of the strategies in supporting ongoing growth and development beyond the mentoring relationship. Furthermore, understanding the participants' perspectives on future faculty meeting participation and their interest in professional development opportunities can inform program organizers about the potential for continued engagement and support. This knowledge can guide the design and implementation of future interventions, ensuring that they align with the participants' needs and interests.

Discussion/Critique

The mentoring intervention had a notable impact on the motivation levels of both mentors and mentees. By coming together to discuss crucial topics related to college and their specific disciplines, the participants experienced increased motivation and engagement. This collaborative environment allowed for the exchange of knowledge and insights, empowering the mentees with information that may have been unanswered since their hiring. Part-time participants benefited from the mentoring intervention as it allowed them to learn about the college community and address any lingering questions or concerns, they may have had. This aspect of the intervention's outcomes aligned with Gappa and Leslie's (1993) findings, which emphasize that motivational factors, such as personal and professional growth, play a significant role in driving the participation of part-time faculty. The mentoring intervention served as a catalyst for motivation and growth among both mentors and mentees. By fostering an open dialogue and knowledge-sharing environment, participants could tap into their intrinsic motivation and develop a sense of belonging within the college community. The mentoring relationship provided guidance, support, and valuable insights, addressing immediate concerns and encouraging long-term personal and professional development. Furthermore, the

intervention contributed to the overall satisfaction and engagement of part-time faculty, who often face unique challenges due to their limited involvement in the college community. By providing them with a platform to connect with mentors and gain a deeper understanding of the college's culture and expectations, the intervention helped bridge the gap between part-time faculty and the institution.

Observing the immediate outcomes of the interventions is challenging due to time constraints. However, the anticipated changes resulting from these interventions revolve around increased participation of part-time mentee participants in various aspects such as meetings, professional development, and collaboration. One significant outcome observed is the satisfaction expressed by the mentees in having a mentor to guide them. This mentorship relationship has provided them with the necessary support and guidance to navigate their roles effectively. The survey results highlight the mentees' desire to actively collaborate and take advantage of learning opportunities through professional development. The mentees have gained confidence and a sense of direction in their professional journeys. They feel more equipped to contribute to meetings and actively participate in discussions. This increased participation benefits the mentees individually and enhances the overall collaboration and knowledge-sharing within the organization. The mentees' commitment to professional development is evident in their desire to engage in learning opportunities. They recognize the value of continuous growth and are driven to enhance their skills and knowledge. This commitment to professional development benefits the mentees' individual growth and contributes to the overall improvement of their performance and effectiveness in their roles. The mentoring interventions have laid the foundation for ongoing growth and development, fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement.

The central concern revolves around the lack of participation from part-time faculty members in quarterly faculty meetings and professional development opportunities. It is crucial to provide these faculty members with experienced and knowledgeable mentors who can guide them in understanding their roles and contributions to the institution to address this issue. This mentorship can improve promotion opportunities and expand knowledge while fostering a sense of belongingness and engagement within the institution. From the beginning of the intervention, it became evident that part-time faculty members highly valued the presence of a mentor to provide guidance along their professional journey. This evidence shows the importance of mentorship and its positive impact on the mentees' experience. However, it is essential to emphasize that the mentor must possess the necessary training and tools to effectively fulfill their role. Etzkorn and Braddock (2020) highlight how important it is for professional mentors to understand their roles and engage in mentoring training to ensure successful outcomes. Without appropriate training, mentoring efforts can fall short of their intended impact.

It is crucial for mentors to be equipped with the knowledge and skills required to support and guide their mentees effectively. This knowledge includes understanding the specific tasks and challenges faced by part-time faculty members and being well-versed in the resources and opportunities available within the institution. The mentor training provided to mentors as part of the implementation ensured that the mentoring process was effective and beneficial for the mentees. Well-prepared mentors can facilitate meaningful discussions, provide relevant resources, and help mentees explore their potential contributions to the institution. This preparation, in turn, can enhance the mentees' engagement and sense of belonging, leading to increased participation in faculty meetings and professional development opportunities.

The identified Problem of Practice revolves around the low participation of part-time faculty members in quarterly faculty meetings and professional development opportunities. This lack of collaboration and teamwork can harm the workplace, including stagnant curriculum advancements, limited engagement in professional growth, a lack of institutional knowledge, and an increased burden on committed faculty members. Unfortunately, there is insufficient data to determine whether the quarterly faculty meeting attendance problem has been fully resolved. However, it is worth noting that one out of the two participants expressed an interest in attending these meetings, indicating a potential positive shift in engagement. This highlights the importance of further investigation and monitoring to assess the effectiveness of interventions in addressing this specific aspect. Adversely, both participants expressed their interest in engaging in professional development opportunities. The mentoring relationship played a crucial role in guiding the mentees and showcasing the various options available for professional development. Moreover, the commitment demonstrated by the mentor to participate alongside the mentees further emphasizes the value and dedication of the mentoring process.

Utilizing mentoring resources such as Canvas, Teams, and other communication platforms provided a conducive environment for discussions on important topics, including professional development. These platforms facilitated knowledge-sharing and the mentees felt encouraged to participate in more activities. For instance, both participants expressed their enthusiasm to join collaborative efforts within their department, such as team teaching, curriculum revisions, and professional development courses. These collaborative initiatives have the potential to foster increased engagement and participation in team meetings, thus potentially addressing the Problem of Practice.

The stakeholders involved in this project have expressed a positive perception of the implemented mentoring program. They view it as a valuable investment in the development and growth of individuals and the organization. Recognizing the potential benefits, stakeholders see the program to enhance employee engagement, productivity, and retention. They understand that formal mentoring programs are a strategic initiative to build a robust talent pipeline and foster a positive organizational culture. While some stakeholders initially had doubts about the effectiveness and impact of mentoring programs, their continued support demonstrates their belief in the program's potential. During meetings and informal conversations, stakeholders actively provided contributions and ideas to enhance the mentoring interventions further.

The participants who have benefited from the mentoring interventions have also demonstrated optimistic viewpoints of the program. They value the chance to learn from experienced mentors, gain new skills, and receive personal and professional development guidance. Mentoring has provided them with support, encouragement, and motivation. It is worth noting that initially, there were concerns about participants feeling overwhelmed by the time commitment or unsure about the value they would receive. During the initial interview, both participants expressed negative past experiences with other mentoring relationships. It is crucial that participants have a clear understanding of the program's benefits and set clear expectations to address these concerns. Additionally, building trust between mentors and mentees is crucial. Some participants may resist engaging in mentoring programs for various reasons, such as a lack of confidence, fear of vulnerability, or perceived time constraints. Overcoming this resistance requires effective communication, addressing individual concerns, and highlighting the program's potential benefits.

While the mentoring intervention for the AIP was beneficial overall, a few unexpected occurrences impacted the program's effectiveness. One of the challenges faced was the limited participation of mentors. Although several mentors were initially invited to participate in the mentoring training, only four could engage due to other commitments. After discussing this situation with stakeholders, it was decided that one mentor participant would execute the intervention with two mentee participants. However, this shortage of participants resulted in limited engagement and progress, although the results were still sufficient to understand if the problem of practice was addressed. Another concern raised by stakeholders was the potential for mentees to have unrealistic expectations of what mentoring can achieve. There was a worry that mentees might expect immediate career advancements or solutions to all their challenges. To address this concern, mentors were responsible for managing expectations and setting realistic goals at the beginning of the mentoring intervention. This crucial step prevents mentees from experiencing disappointment or frustration.

Additionally, there was some apprehension regarding the potential mismatching of mentors and mentees. While a mismatched mentoring relationship did not occur in this program, it is acknowledged that sometimes, the pairing of mentors and mentees may not be suitable. Research by O'Hara et al. (2020) suggested that mentoring relationships are more likely to be successful when there is a good match between the mentor and mentee regarding personality, communication style, and professional goals. Mismatched personalities, conflicting objectives, or communication styles can hinder the effectiveness of the mentoring relationship. To minimize such occurrences, it is essential to conduct thorough assessments and provide training to mentors and mentees, ensuring compatibility and alignment of goals and communication styles.

While the implementation stage of the mentoring program showed promising results, there are areas that could be improved to yield even better ones. One notable aspect is the duration of the mentoring relationship, as both mentors and mentees felt that the five-week intervention plan was insufficient. To maximize the program's impact, it is recommended that future iterations extend the mentoring period to allow for a more comprehensive evaluation of the intervention's outcomes. To enhance the effectiveness of the mentoring program, mentors should be encouraged to offer ongoing support and resources to their mentees throughout the entire duration of the program. This could involve providing access to relevant training materials, facilitating networking opportunities, and offering guidance from program coordinators. By maintaining regular communication and support, the mentoring experience can be further enriched, leading to more positive outcomes. Considering these potential modifications, it is plausible that the program's results could have been improved. By extending the duration of the mentoring relationship and implementing measures to ensure ongoing support, the program could have fostered even more significant growth and development among the participants.

While the mentoring program exhibited some positive outcomes, it is crucial to acknowledge the limitations observed throughout the study. Time commitment emerged as a significant challenge for mentors and mentees as participants struggled to balance their busy schedules and competing priorities. This was particularly evident during the recruiting phase, where the number of mentors who joined the training fell short of expectations. In discussions with the Dean, the lack of commitment was highlighted, which aligns with Lunsford et al.'s (2018) findings, where the scarcity of senior faculty mentors hindered support for underrepresented faculty. The difficulty in balancing mentoring activities with other obligations

inevitably restricted the availability and commitment of participants. This limitation must be considered in the next phase of the program.

Furthermore, identifying qualified mentors who possess the expertise and experience proved to be a challenge. Organizations may encounter difficulties in recruiting mentors with the desired skills or industry knowledge, leading to a potential shortage of mentors for all interested mentees. It is crucial to address these limitations to enhance the effectiveness and impact of the mentoring program. Strategies such as providing flexibility in scheduling, offering incentives for mentor participation, and implementing targeted recruitment efforts to attract mentors with the desired qualifications can help overcome these obstacles. By addressing these limitations, the program can improve the availability and commitment of participants, ensuring a more robust and successful mentoring experience for all involved.

The influence of organizational power dynamics can present significant challenges and tensions within mentoring interventions. A specific instance arose during the initial interview, where a participant expressed concern about how much information shared in the mentoring session would be accessible to the department chair. To address this, confidentiality was emphasized, emphasizing the importance of maintaining privacy and encouraging open sharing of thoughts and experiences. Participants were assured that findings from interviews and surveys would be consolidated and shared in a summarized form to protect their anonymity. Several measures were implemented throughout the implementation stages of the mentoring intervention to uphold ethical and scholarly standards and foster trustworthiness and credibility. All individuals involved were provided with comprehensive information regarding the program's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits before participation. Informed consent was obtained from participants, ensuring their voluntary engagement and understanding of their

rights. Confidentiality was emphasized, assuring participants that their personal identifying information would remain protected throughout the intervention and debriefing processes. Data was anonymized to safeguard privacy and mitigate potential harm or negative consequences. The mentoring intervention encompassed research and evaluation, so obtaining ethics approval from the institutional review board was imperative. This step ensured that the intervention adhered to ethical guidelines and principles, reassuring that the program was conducted ethically and in accordance with established standards.

Implications for Professional Practice

The development of a mentoring program for part-time faculty members, as explored in this project, offers significant implications for professional practice both locally and in similar organizations. Drawing on Danaei (2019), the project highlights how including part-time faculty in key institutional activities, such as setting learning objectives and selecting textbooks, can enhance their engagement and professional development. The success of this mentoring program not only addresses the unique needs of part-time faculty but also serves as a replicable model for other institutions looking to improve collaboration and support among their staff. By adopting and adapting the following strategies, other organizations can similarly enhance their part-time faculty's engagement, leading to overall institutional improvement:

1. Integrating part-time faculty into key institutional discussions via a mentoring program.
This strategy boosts their engagement and sense of belonging and contributes to the institution's success by leveraging their insights and expertise. Mentors are crucial in facilitating this inclusion, enhancing the overall academic environment.
2. Enhancement collaboration among part-time faculty through mentorship. This approach enables part-time faculty to better grasp their responsibilities and the importance of their

input, fostering more outstanding teamwork. As a result, there is a collective push towards advancing the curriculum and achieving institutional goals, demonstrating the mentorship program's role in promoting a more unified and effective academic community.

3. Focusing on leveraging mentorship to boost professional development among part-time faculty. Through mentor guidance, part-time faculty are encouraged to engage in various professional development activities, enhancing their skills and teaching methodologies. This engagement benefits the institution and its students and facilitates the transfer of valuable institutional knowledge from full-time to part-time faculty. Such a strategy ensures consistency in educational quality and institutional practices, reinforcing the organization's effectiveness and resilience against faculty turnover.
4. Catering to the unique needs of part-time faculty. Through a needs assessment, the project pinpointed the specific challenges part-time faculty face, such as difficulties attending faculty meetings and engaging in professional development. . This insight led to creating solutions, such as the mentoring program, demonstrating the effectiveness of customizing interventions to meet an organization's distinct needs and obstacles.
5. The necessity of institutional support and resources for successful change implementation, specifically for a mentoring program. This program necessitated the involvement of full-time faculty as mentors, requiring their commitment alongside additional resources like training and communication tools. The project also sheds light on the crucial roles that organizational culture and communication play in making changes effective. It tackled the issue of part-time faculty feeling marginalized from

institutional dialogues and decisions, aiming to foster inclusivity by integrating them through the mentorship of full-time faculty members.

6. Ongoing evaluation and adaptation in the mentoring program's implementation. Initially identifying part-time faculty's specific challenges through a needs assessment, the project established a foundation for assessing the program's impact and facilitating timely modifications to meet the faculty's needs better. This approach ensures the mentoring program remains effective and responsive to evolving challenges.
7. Enhancing faculty engagement and commitment through several fundamental changes. Primarily, it recommends prolonging the mentoring relationship duration, allowing deeper trust and continuous guidance, which boosts part-time faculty motivation and commitment. Additionally, consistent support, including resources and regular check-ins, is vital for sustaining motivation. Recognizing and appreciating part-time faculty's contributions is also crucial, as it nurtures a feeling of value and commitment, encouraging further involvement in college activities. Collectively, these strategies aim to improve overall satisfaction and dedication among part-time faculty members.
8. Effective communication and providing necessary tools and resources to improve faculty engagement and commitment. By facilitating clear communication, colleges can better engage faculty in goal setting and progress tracking, enhancing their motivation. Additionally, equipping part-time faculty with essential resources supports their active participation and further boosts their motivation, highlighting the role of communication and resources in creating a supportive academic environment.
9. Motivating full-time faculty to become mentors by offering enticing incentives, including extra compensation, professional development opportunities, or recognition. This strategy

expands the pool of mentors, ensuring ample support for part-time faculty. It reflects the organization's dedication to faculty growth, which, in turn, boosts engagement and contributes to the organization's success.

The mentorship theory, particularly Kram's (1983) categorization of mentoring functions, was a crucial theoretical underpinning for the proposed intervention in this Advanced Improvement Project (AIP). The project validated Kram's framework through detailed analysis and observation of established mentoring relationships, highlighting its relevance in guiding the evaluation of mentorship functions within the program. Key findings include the confirmation of career-related mentoring functions, where mentors significantly contributed to mentees' goal setting, skill development, and career progression through guidance and support. Additionally, the project underscored the importance of psychological mentoring functions, with mentors providing encouragement, support, and a safe environment for mentees to voice their challenges, fostering their self-confidence and resilience. The role-model function of mentors was also validated, with mentors exemplifying professionalism, leadership, and ethical behavior, thereby inspiring mentees to emulate these qualities. This comprehensive analysis confirmed the theoretical assumptions of Kram's mentorship model, illustrating the multifaceted roles of mentors and their profound influence on participants' professional and personal growth.

Recommendations

To effectively motivate and secure long-term commitment from part-time faculty, focusing on strategies that enhance their engagement and professional growth is recommended.

Key recommendations include:

1. **Boost Commitment:** A reported lack of commitment from mentors, as shared by participants reflecting on past experiences, exacerbates the challenges for part-time

faculty, who already face difficulties accessing institutional support and recognition, leading to feelings of isolation. To address these issues, targeted recruitment efforts, including offering scheduling flexibility and incentives like recognition or professional development opportunities, are recommended to boost mentor participation and commitment. Gappa and Leslie (1993) discuss how incentives can drive increased participation. Such incentives motivate mentors to dedicate their time and expertise to develop significant connections with their mentees.

2. **Extending Mentoring Relationships:** Extending the duration of mentoring relationships has emerged as a critical need from feedback and literature, highlighting that mentors and mentees benefit from more extended engagement periods to develop meaningful connections, share knowledge, and achieve program goals. Feedback from mentors indicates a consensus that the current duration of mentoring programs is too short, underscoring the need for extended time frames to allow for the establishment of rapport and effective mentorship. Research by Buch et al. (2023) and Luna (2018) supports the idea that longer-term mentoring relationships can overcome barriers to engagement and facilitate collaborative projects between mentors and mentees, enhancing the educational experience.
3. **Providing Ongoing Support:** After the formal mentoring relationship concludes, mentors must persist in offering support to their mentees. Regular, open communication is crucial for maintaining a solid connection, enabling the mentee to continue benefiting from the mentor's experience and support. Research by Fitzgerald and McNamara (2021) underscores the importance of sustained mentor involvement and communication in

fostering a lasting and impactful mentor-mentee relationship. This enduring support plays a pivotal role in the long-term success and development of the mentee.

4. **Fostering Collaboration:** Emphasizing collaboration within mentoring programs, particularly in higher education, can significantly bridge the gap between part-time and full-time faculty, fostering improved educational quality, as noted by Danaei (2019). Despite time constraints limiting collaboration evaluation in this specific project, the consensus in literature and initiatives like Bickerstaff and Chavarín's (2018) student success movement at community colleges highlight the importance of collaborative engagement among faculty. Project participants expressed interest in future collaboration, suggesting it could improve mentoring and student success. Allocating time and resources for collaborative activities, such as joint projects and workshops, is advised to enhance mentoring outcomes.
5. **Establishing Communication Channels:** It is recommended to prioritize simple communication platforms like text messaging for efficiency, supported by Mackessy et al. (2019), to enhance virtual mentoring programs. Creating a centralized mentoring hub can streamline access to tools and improve communication. Additionally, it is crucial to consider millennials' preferences for technology-based communication and their desire for regular feedback, as Waljee et al. (2020) highlighted. Adapting to these digital communication methods can strengthen mentor-mentee relationships and support millennial learners' success by meeting their continuous learning and engagement expectations.
6. **Supplying Appropriate Tools:** Embracing virtual tools and resources enhances the engagement of online part-time faculty in mentoring programs, overcoming distance and

scheduling challenges. Virtual environments facilitate flexible, effective communication and collaboration, allowing interactive discussions and problem-solving despite physical separation. McAtee and Huston (2023) emphasize the value of the e-lounge, a virtual space within Canvas software, as a key to successful online mentoring. The e-lounge provides 24/7 access to a wide array of resources, including instructional videos, tutorials, and teaching tools, thereby improving accessibility, convenience, and participation in the mentoring process for online part-time faculty.

7. Next Cycle of Inquiry: The next inquiry cycle should assess the mentoring program's long-term effectiveness to ensure it meets its goals. Understanding the program's sustained impact will highlight areas needing improvement and participant satisfaction, offering insights for future enhancements. Feedback from mentors and participants will identify specific aspects requiring attention, such as commitment levels and the effectiveness of resources. Evaluating long-term impact supports data-driven decisions on resource allocation and program adjustments, enhancing overall effectiveness. This approach emphasizes continuous improvement and adaptation to meet evolving needs.

CONCLUSION

The project identified the problem of low participation of part-time faculty members in faculty meetings and professional development opportunities. This lack of collaboration had negative consequences, such as limited curriculum advancements and increased workload for committed faculty members. The project implemented strategies to address this, including a mentoring program to improve engagement and foster collaboration. The program enhances professional development, strengthens the organizational culture, and ensures equitable resource allocation.

The site, Southeastern Community College, implemented a mentoring program to address part-time faculty members' low participation and engagement in faculty meetings and activities. The program connected part-time faculty with full-time faculty mentors to provide guidance and support. A needs assessment was conducted to understand the challenges faced by part-time faculty, and the program creates a collaborative and inclusive environment for knowledge sharing and professional development. Data was collected throughout the implementation, and adjustments were made based on feedback received. The program's effectiveness was evaluated through interviews, surveys, journal analysis, and collaboration with program coordinators. The positive impact on collaboration and engagement was shared with stakeholders.

The project's results have provided valuable knowledge on improving faculty engagement and professional development. Implementing a mentoring program for part-time faculty members can foster collaboration, knowledge sharing, and satisfaction. Involving part-time and full-time faculty members in the program strengthens the organizational culture. Resource allocation and support, including training and access to tools, are essential for success. Offering incentives to full-time faculty members to become mentors can enhance the program's

effectiveness. By implementing these recommendations, the organization can create a supportive and collaborative environment for faculty members' success and satisfaction.

The project's results suggest several changes to improve faculty engagement and commitment. Extending the duration of mentoring relationships and offering ongoing support and resources can positively impact motivation and commitment. Recognizing and appreciating the contributions of part-time faculty members can foster a sense of value and commitment. Promoting collaboration and knowledge sharing among faculty members enhances motivation and inclusivity. Effective communication channels and access to appropriate tools and resources are crucial for engagement.

In conclusion, the project's findings emphasize the significant impact that a mentoring program can have on part-time faculty members. By implementing such a program, collaboration and knowledge sharing are fostered, leading to increased satisfaction among faculty. Additionally, the program contributes to strengthening the organizational culture, promoting a sense of unity and shared goals. Moreover, the program ensures equitable resource allocation, ensuring all faculty members can access the necessary tools and support for their professional development. Overall, the findings underscore the importance of a mentoring program in creating a supportive and inclusive environment for part-time faculty, ultimately benefiting both the faculty and the organization.

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